

Ecosphere - Intrinsic and extrinsic drivers shape frugivore functional diversity within a tree population

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Appendix S2

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1 Section 1: Introduction

This document reproduces the fitting procedure of Bayesian models from the article **Intrinsic and extrinsic drivers modulate the functional diversity of frugivorous birds interacting with individual trees within a population**. It is organized into sections showing the data wrangling operations for preparing the data, the models in mathematical notation, Stan code, fitting procedure, models diagnostics, estimation of condition effect, and simulations of interventions.

2 Section 2: Data wrangling

Loading packages:

```
sapply(c('dplyr', 'ggplot2', 'patchwork',
        'rethinking', 'cmdstanr', 'magrittr',
        'forcats', 'cowplot', 'readxl', 'sf'), library, character.only = T)

source('functions_mod_diagnostics.r')
```

The following code loads the data, transforms latitude/longitude coordinates to UTM for each individual, and generates the distance matrix among individuals. The additional code is used to format the R object holding the data set.

```
d <- read_xlsx('full_data_for_model_03_apr_25.xlsx', sheet = 1,
              col_names = T, na = 'NA')

cords <- d[, c("Individual", "Lon", "Lat")]

# latitude/longitude coordinates to UTM
rs_sf <- st_as_sf(cords, coords = c("Lon", "Lat"), crs = 4326)

rs_utm <- st_transform(rs_sf, crs = 31982)

utm_coords <- st_coordinates(rs_utm) |>
  as_tibble() |>
  rename(x_utm = X, y_utm = Y)

# distance matrix
dist_inds <-
  sapply(seq_along(utm_coords$x_utm), FUN =
        function(i) {
          x <- utm_coords$x_utm[i]
          y <- utm_coords$y_utm[i]

          dist <- sqrt((x - utm_coords$x_utm)^2 + (y - utm_coords$y_utm)^2)

        })

colnames(dist_inds) <- d$Individual
rownames(dist_inds) <- d$Individual
```

```

responses <- d[, grep('obs_22', colnames(d))]
predictors <- d[, c('S', "Height", "Crop", "Duration",
                  "Fruit", "Tree", "Infrastructure")]

predictors <- apply(predictors, 2, function(x) as.vector(scale(x)))

d$ind_id <- as.numeric(gsub('^([a-z]*)([0-9]*)$', '\\3', d$Individual))

dat_1 <- cbind(d[, "ind_id"], responses, predictors) |> as_tibble()

dat_1 <-
  dat_1 |>
  rename(S_std = S)

dat_1$S <- sapply(d$S, function(x) if (x == 0) 0.1 else x)

colnames(dat_1) <- tolower(colnames(dat_1))

```

3 Section 3: Mathematical notation of the models

We aimed to assess the effect of intrinsic and extrinsic drivers on bird functional diversity (FD) while accounting for the effect of species richness on FRic, FEve, and FReg. To do so, we used a Bayesian hierarchical approach to model the effect of predictors on species richness (S) and FD metrics as a set of hierarchical linear equations:

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_i &\sim \text{Student-T}(\nu = 7, \mu 1_i, \sigma 1) \\
 \mu 1_i &= \alpha_1 + \tau 1_{\text{individual } i} + \beta_1 \times \text{crop size}_i + \\
 &\beta_2 \times \text{height}_i + \beta_3 \times \text{fruiting duration}_i + \\
 &\beta_4 \times \text{fruit density}_i + \beta_5 \times \text{tree cover}_i + \\
 &\beta_6 \times \text{infrastructure cover}_i
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 FD_{\text{metric } i} &\sim \text{Student-T}(\nu = 7, \mu 2_i, \sigma 2) \\
 \mu 2_i &= \alpha_2 + \tau 2_{\text{individual } i} + \beta_7 \times S_i \\
 &\beta_8 \times \text{crop size}_i + \beta_9 \times \text{height}_i + \\
 &\beta_{10} \times \text{fruiting duration}_i + \\
 &\beta_{11} \times \text{fruit density}_i + \\
 &\beta_{12} \times \text{tree cover}_i + \\
 &\beta_{13} \times \text{infrastructure cover}_i
 \end{aligned}$$

We assign prior probabilities to the intercept (i.e., α)

$$\alpha_1 \sim \text{Normal}(0, 1)$$

$$\alpha_2 \sim \text{Normal}(0, 1)$$

Gaussian processes for accounting spatial correlation among individuals (i.e., τ parameter). We used a quadratic kernel (i.e., $k(d_i, d_j)$ in the formula below) to construct the covariance matrix ($K[i, j]$) and a non-centered parametrization through a Cholesky decomposition of the covariance matrix.

$$k(i, j) = \eta^2 \exp(-\rho^2 D_{ij}^2) + \delta_{ij} \times 0.01$$

$$K[i, j] = k(i, j)$$

$$LK = K \times K^T$$

$$\tau_{1,2} = LK \times z_{\tau_{1,2}}$$

$$z_{\tau} \sim \text{Normal}(0, 1)$$

$$\eta \sim \text{exponential}(4)$$

$$\delta \sim \text{exponential}(1)$$

Priors for slope parameters

$$\beta_{1, \dots, 13} \sim \text{Normal}(0, 0.25)$$

Priors for dispersion parameters

$$\sigma_{1,2} \sim \text{exponential}(1)$$

Full model:

$$\begin{aligned} S_i &\sim \text{Student-T}(\nu = 7, \mu 1_i, \sigma 1) \\ \mu 1_i &= \alpha_1 + \tau 1_{\text{individual } i} + \beta_1 \times \text{crop size}_i + \\ &\beta_2 \times \text{height}_i + \beta_3 \times \text{fruiting duration}_i + \\ &\beta_4 \times \text{fruit density}_i + \beta_5 \times \text{tree cover}_i + \\ &\beta_6 \times \text{infrastructure cover}_i \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} FD_{\text{metric } i} &\sim \text{Student-T}(\nu = 7, \mu 2_i, \sigma 2) \\ \mu 2_i &= \alpha_2 + \tau 2_{\text{individual } i} + \beta_7 \times S_i \\ &\beta_8 \times \text{crop size}_i + \beta_9 \times \text{height}_i + \\ &\beta_{10} \times \text{fruiting duration}_i + \\ &\beta_{11} \times \text{fruit density}_i + \\ &\beta_{12} \times \text{tree cover}_i + \\ &\beta_{13} \times \text{infrastructure cover}_i \end{aligned}$$

$$\alpha_1 \sim \text{Normal}(0, 1)$$

$$\alpha_2 \sim \text{Normal}(0, 1)$$

$$k(i, j) = \eta^2 \exp(-\rho^2 D_{ij}^2) + \delta_{ij} \times 0.01$$

$$K[i, j] = k(i, j)$$

$$LK = K \times K^T$$

$$\tau_{1,2} = LK \times z_{\tau_{1,2}}$$

$$z_{\tau} \sim \text{Normal}(0, 1)$$

$$\eta \sim \text{exponential}(4)$$

$$\delta \sim \text{exponential}(1)$$

$$\beta_1, \dots, \beta_{13} \sim \text{Normal}(0, 0.25)$$

$$\sigma_{1,2} \sim \text{exponential}(1)$$

NOTE: The models for FRic, FDiv and FReg have the same structure. Therefore, the above mathematical version can be applied to all of them.

4 Section 4: Model FRic

Formatting the data frame in a list object.

```

dat <- lapply(dat_1, function(x) x)

dat$N <- length(dat$ind_id)
dat$N_ind <- max(dat$ind_id)
dat$dist_mat <- dist_inds
names(dat)[2:4] <- c('fric', 'fdiv', 'freg')

dat$fric <- as.vector(scale(dat$fric))

```

S4.1 Stan code

```

cat(file = 'model_FRic.stan',
    '\n\n',
    'functions {\n',
    '  matrix cov_GPL2(matrix x,\n',
    '                  real eta,\n',
    '                  real rho,\n',
    '                  real delta) {\n\n',
    '    int N = dims(x)[1];\n',
    '    matrix[N, N] K;\n',
    '    matrix[N, N] L_K;\n\n',
    '    for (i in 1:(N-1)) {\n',
    '      K[i, i] = eta + delta;\n',
    '      for (j in (i+1):N) {\n',
    '        K[i, j] = eta * exp(-rho * square(x[i, j]));\n',
    '        K[j, i] = K[i, j];\n',
    '      }\n',
    '    }\n\n',
    '    K[N, N] = eta + delta;\n',
    '    L_K = cholesky_decompose(K);\n',
    '    return L_K;\n',
    '  }\n',
    '}\n\n',
    'data {\n',
    '  int N;\n',
    '  int N_ind;

```

```

matrix[N_ind, N_ind] dist_mat;
array[N] int ind_id;
vector[N] fric;
vector[N] s_std;
vector[N] height;
vector[N] crop;
vector[N] duration;
vector[N] fruit;
vector[N] tree;
vector[N] infrastructure;
}

parameters {

  // model S
  real alpha_S;
  real<lower = 0> sigma_S;
  real beta_forest_S;
  real beta_height_S;
  real beta_crop_S;
  real beta_duration_S;
  real beta_fruit_S;
  real beta_urban_S;
  vector[N_ind] z_ind_S;
  real<lower = 0> eta_S;
  real<lower = 0> rho_S;

  // model FRic
  real alpha_FRic;
  real<lower = 0> sigma_FRic;
  real beta_S;
  real beta_forest_FRic;
  real beta_height_FRic;
  real beta_crop_FRic;
  real beta_duration_FRic;
  real beta_fruit_FRic;
  real beta_urban_FRic;
  vector[N_ind] z_ind_FRic;
  real<lower = 0> eta_FRic;
  real<lower = 0> rho_FRic;
}

```

```

transformed parameters {
  // pars S
  vector[N_ind] ind_S;
  matrix[N_ind, N_ind] L_K_S;
  L_K_S = cov_GPL2(dist_mat, eta_S, rho_S, 0.001);
  ind_S = L_K_S * z_ind_S;

  // pars FRic
  vector[N_ind] ind_FRic;
  matrix[N_ind, N_ind] L_K_FRic;
  L_K_FRic = cov_GPL2(dist_mat, eta_FRic, rho_FRic, 0.001);
  ind_FRic = L_K_FRic * z_ind_FRic;
}

model {

  // prior S
  alpha_S ~ normal(0, 1);
  sigma_S ~ exponential(1);
  z_ind_S ~ normal(0, 0.25);
  eta_S ~ exponential(4);
  rho_S ~ exponential(1);
  beta_forest_S ~ normal(0, 0.25);
  beta_height_S ~ normal(0, 0.25);
  beta_crop_S ~ normal(0, 0.25);
  beta_duration_S ~ normal(0, 0.25);
  beta_fruit_S ~ normal(0, 0.25);
  beta_urban_S ~ normal(0, 0.25);

  // prior FRic
  alpha_FRic ~ normal(0, 1);
  sigma_FRic ~ exponential(1);
  z_ind_FRic ~ normal(0, 0.25);
  eta_FRic ~ exponential(4);
  rho_FRic ~ exponential(1);
  beta_forest_FRic ~ normal(0, 0.25);
  beta_height_FRic ~ normal(0, 0.25);
  beta_crop_FRic ~ normal(0, 0.25);
  beta_duration_FRic ~ normal(0, 0.25);
  beta_fruit_FRic ~ normal(0, 0.25);
  beta_urban_FRic ~ normal(0, 0.25);
  beta_S ~ normal(0, 1);
}

```

```

// model S
s_std ~ student_t(7,
    alpha_S +
    beta_forest_S * tree +
    beta_height_S * height +
    beta_crop_S * crop +
    beta_duration_S * duration +
    beta_fruit_S * fruit +
    beta_urban_S * infrastructure +
    ind_S[ind_id], sigma_S);

// model FRic
fric ~ student_t(7,
    alpha_FRic +
    beta_S * s_std +
    beta_forest_FRic * tree +
    beta_height_FRic * height +
    beta_crop_FRic * crop +
    beta_duration_FRic * duration +
    beta_fruit_FRic * fruit +
    beta_urban_FRic * infrastructure +
    ind_FRic[ind_id], sigma_FRic);
}

generated quantities {
    array[N] real ppcheck_S;
    array[N] real ppcheck_FRic;
    vector[N] mu_S;
    vector[N] mu_FRic;

    mu_S = alpha_S +
        beta_forest_S * tree +
        beta_height_S * height +
        beta_crop_S * crop +
        beta_duration_S * duration +
        beta_fruit_S * fruit +
        beta_urban_S * infrastructure +
        ind_S[ind_id];

    ppcheck_S = student_t_rng(7, mu_S, sigma_S);
}

```

```

mu_FRic = alpha_FRic +
  beta_S * s_std +
  beta_forest_FRic * tree +
  beta_height_FRic * height +
  beta_crop_FRic * crop +
  beta_duration_FRic * duration +
  beta_fruit_FRic * fruit +
  beta_urban_FRic * infrastructure +
  ind_FRic[ind_id];

ppcheck_FRic = student_t_rng(7, mu_FRic, sigma_FRic);

}
')
```

S4.2 Fitting the model

```

file <- paste0(getwd(), '/model_FRic.stan')
fit_FRic <- cmdstan_model(file, compile = T)

indx_na_vars <-
  unlist(lapply(dat, function(x) sum(is.na(x)) == 0),
         use.names = F)

mod_FRic <-
  fit_FRic$sample(
    data = dat[indx_na_vars],
    iter_warmup = 500,
    iter_sampling = 4e3,
    chains = 3,
    parallel_chains = 3,
    refresh = 500,
    thin = 3,
    seed = 5
  )
)
```

S4.3 Model diagnostics

```
sum_FRic <- mod_FRic$summary()

mod_diagnostics(mod_FRic, sum_FRic)
```


Figure S1: Rhat values vs effective sampling size (ess). Rhat < 1.05 indicates that the Markov Chains converged to the same stationary distribution. ess must be at least 100 in order to be reliable

```
indx_pars <-
  c(grep('^beta', sum_FRic$variable),
    grep('^sigma', sum_FRic$variable),
    grep('^alpha', sum_FRic$variable),
    grep('^ind', sum_FRic$variable))

par(mfrow = c(4, 5), mar = c(4, 4, 1, 1))
for (i in 1:17) {
  trace_plot(mod_FRic, sum_FRic$variable[indx_pars[i]], 3)
}
par(mfrow = c(1, 1))
```


Figure S2: Trace plots showing chain convergence per parameter

```

ppcheck_S <- mod_FRic$draws('ppcheck_S', format = 'matrix')
ppcheck_FRic <- mod_FRic$draws('ppcheck_FRic', format = 'matrix')

par(mfrow = c(1, 2), mar = c(4, 4, 1, 1))
plot(density(dat$s_std), xlim = c(-4, 5),
     ylim = c(0, 0.7), main = '', xlab = 'N species (z-scores)')
for (i in 1:500) lines(density(ppcheck_S[i, ]), lwd = 0.1)
lines(density(dat$s_std), col = 'red', lwd = 1.5)

plot(density(dat$fric), xlim = c(-4, 4),
     ylim = c(0, 0.7), main = '', xlab = 'FRic (z-scores)')
for (i in 1:500) lines(density(ppcheck_FRic[i, ]), lwd = 0.1)
lines(density(dat$fric), col = 'red', lwd = 1.5)

```


Figure S3: Posterior predictive checks of the model describing species richness and FRic of the birds assemblage

```
par(mfrow = c(1, 1))
```

```
par(mfrow = c(2, 2))
plot(density(apply(ppcheck_S, 1, mean)), xlab = 'AVG. S (estimated)',
     main = '')
abline(v = mean(dat$s_std), col = 'red')
plot(density(apply(ppcheck_S, 1, sd)), xlab = 'SD. S (estimated)',
     main = '')
abline(v = sd(dat$s_std), col = 'red')

plot(density(apply(ppcheck_FRic, 1, mean)), xlab = 'AVG. FRic (estimated)',
     main = '')
abline(v = mean(dat$fric), col = 'red')
plot(density(apply(ppcheck_FRic, 1, sd)), xlab = 'SD. FRic (estimated)',
     main = '')
abline(v = sd(dat$fric), col = 'red')
```


Figure S4: Observed average and SD from species richness and FRic against the estimated by the model

```
par(mfrow = c(1, 1))
```

```
indx_pars <-
  c(grep('^beta', sum_FRic$variable),
    grep('^sigma', sum_FRic$variable),
    grep('^alpha', sum_FRic$variable),
    grep('^ind', sum_FRic$variable))

text <-
  'Average, SD, confidence intervals and metrics of sampling
  diagnostics for the parameters estimating species richness
  and FRic of the birds assemblage'

knitr::kable(
  sum_FRic[indx_pars, ],
  digits = 2,
  caption = text
)
```

Table S1: Average, SD, confidence intervals and metrics of sampling diagnostics for the parameters estimating species richness and FRic of the birds assemblage

variable	mean	median	sd	mad	q5	q95	rhat	ess_bulk	ess_tail
beta_forest_S	-0.04	-0.04	0.15	0.15	-0.28	0.22	1	3812.82	3731.72
beta_height_S	0.25	0.25	0.16	0.16	-0.02	0.51	1	4133.42	3546.03
beta_crop_S	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.17	-0.10	0.44	1	4603.34	3777.47
beta_duration_S	0.16	0.16	0.17	0.17	-0.12	0.44	1	4023.65	3689.45
beta_fruit_S	0.11	0.11	0.17	0.17	-0.17	0.39	1	4260.49	4025.68
beta_urban_S	-0.19	-0.20	0.15	0.14	-0.43	0.05	1	4675.84	3914.21
beta_S	0.52	0.51	0.17	0.17	0.24	0.82	1	4322.51	3658.69
beta_forest_FRic	-0.12	-0.12	0.14	0.14	-0.36	0.12	1	4462.27	3740.59
beta_height_FRic	0.24	0.24	0.15	0.14	0.00	0.48	1	4484.65	3721.99
beta_crop_FRic	0.11	0.12	0.16	0.16	-0.16	0.36	1	4242.41	3779.42
beta_duration_FRic	-0.06	-0.06	0.15	0.15	-0.30	0.18	1	4354.60	3412.32
beta_fruit_FRic	-0.05	-0.05	0.15	0.14	-0.30	0.18	1	4084.22	3507.94
beta_urban_FRic	-0.07	-0.07	0.14	0.14	-0.30	0.16	1	4024.73	3543.43
sigma_S	0.76	0.75	0.13	0.13	0.57	1.00	1	4137.66	3934.58
sigma_FRic	0.62	0.61	0.11	0.11	0.46	0.83	1	3901.33	3942.50
alpha_S	-0.03	-0.04	0.16	0.16	-0.30	0.23	1	4719.94	3971.90
alpha_FRic	0.00	0.00	0.14	0.13	-0.23	0.22	1	4429.04	4047.60
ind_S[1]	-0.02	-0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.24	0.17	1	4636.69	3971.96
ind_S[2]	-0.02	-0.01	0.13	0.09	-0.24	0.17	1	4374.95	3778.13
ind_S[3]	-0.02	-0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.23	0.17	1	4205.44	3743.43
ind_S[4]	0.02	0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.18	0.22	1	4369.42	3894.59
ind_S[5]	0.00	0.00	0.12	0.09	-0.20	0.21	1	4329.20	3930.68
ind_S[6]	0.03	0.01	0.13	0.09	-0.16	0.25	1	4620.10	3484.52
ind_S[7]	0.00	0.00	0.12	0.09	-0.19	0.21	1	4619.64	3812.31
ind_S[8]	-0.02	-0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.23	0.17	1	4475.08	3385.75
ind_S[9]	0.01	0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.19	0.22	1	4219.28	3845.60
ind_S[10]	0.01	0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.19	0.21	1	4777.27	3880.60
ind_S[11]	0.03	0.01	0.13	0.09	-0.17	0.26	1	4649.78	3913.14
ind_S[12]	-0.02	-0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.23	0.17	1	4583.94	3789.36
ind_S[13]	0.01	0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.18	0.22	1	4373.34	3802.21
ind_S[14]	-0.01	0.00	0.12	0.09	-0.22	0.18	1	4292.87	3638.53
ind_S[15]	0.00	0.00	0.13	0.09	-0.21	0.20	1	4499.19	3838.02
ind_S[16]	-0.02	-0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.23	0.16	1	4502.75	3612.52
ind_S[17]	0.03	0.02	0.13	0.10	-0.16	0.25	1	4284.98	3546.82
ind_S[18]	-0.01	-0.01	0.13	0.09	-0.23	0.17	1	4374.92	3749.70
ind_S[19]	-0.01	-0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.22	0.19	1	3718.57	3397.65
ind_S[20]	0.03	0.01	0.13	0.09	-0.16	0.25	1	4246.93	3742.59
ind_S[21]	-0.03	-0.01	0.13	0.10	-0.24	0.17	1	4784.39	3918.38

variable	mean	median	sd	mad	q5	q95	rhat	ess_bulk	ess_tail
ind_S[22]	-0.02	-0.01	0.13	0.09	-0.23	0.18	1	4441.77	3617.95
ind_S[23]	0.01	0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.18	0.22	1	4417.74	3976.34
ind_S[24]	0.00	0.00	0.12	0.09	-0.20	0.19	1	4644.25	3934.17
ind_S[25]	0.00	0.00	0.12	0.09	-0.20	0.20	1	4464.05	3488.49
ind_S[26]	-0.01	-0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.23	0.18	1	4553.94	3955.34
ind_S[27]	0.00	0.00	0.12	0.09	-0.20	0.20	1	4543.79	3388.63
ind_S[28]	0.01	0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.18	0.21	1	4252.57	3913.41
ind_S[29]	0.01	0.01	0.13	0.09	-0.18	0.23	1	4735.78	3837.79
ind_FRic[1]	0.00	0.00	0.12	0.09	-0.19	0.20	1	4408.44	3419.21
ind_FRic[2]	0.03	0.02	0.12	0.09	-0.15	0.24	1	4538.65	3932.35
ind_FRic[3]	-0.01	-0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.22	0.18	1	4327.66	3914.89
ind_FRic[4]	0.02	0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.16	0.24	1	4589.80	4004.37
ind_FRic[5]	-0.02	-0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.23	0.18	1	4372.52	3627.14
ind_FRic[6]	-0.01	-0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.20	0.18	1	4419.52	3727.91
ind_FRic[7]	0.01	0.00	0.12	0.09	-0.19	0.20	1	4535.07	3934.05
ind_FRic[8]	0.00	0.00	0.12	0.09	-0.20	0.19	1	4701.60	3975.92
ind_FRic[9]	0.02	0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.17	0.22	1	4555.21	3838.54
ind_FRic[10]	0.00	0.00	0.12	0.09	-0.20	0.19	1	4454.00	3486.96
ind_FRic[11]	-0.02	-0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.23	0.17	1	4587.87	3857.24
ind_FRic[12]	-0.03	-0.02	0.13	0.09	-0.25	0.16	1	4736.63	3998.46
ind_FRic[13]	0.04	0.02	0.13	0.09	-0.14	0.27	1	4422.99	3729.38
ind_FRic[14]	-0.02	-0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.23	0.16	1	4323.72	3663.44
ind_FRic[15]	0.01	0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.17	0.22	1	4431.50	3926.83
ind_FRic[16]	-0.03	-0.02	0.12	0.09	-0.25	0.15	1	4403.38	3834.32
ind_FRic[17]	-0.01	-0.01	0.13	0.09	-0.23	0.18	1	4353.83	3923.74
ind_FRic[18]	0.01	0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.20	0.21	1	4283.44	3830.91
ind_FRic[19]	0.02	0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.16	0.22	1	4739.81	3851.82
ind_FRic[20]	-0.02	-0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.24	0.16	1	4439.44	3893.03
ind_FRic[21]	-0.04	-0.02	0.13	0.09	-0.27	0.14	1	4330.85	3794.78
ind_FRic[22]	0.01	0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.17	0.22	1	4594.49	3802.74
ind_FRic[23]	-0.02	-0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.22	0.17	1	4369.15	3826.32
ind_FRic[24]	0.03	0.02	0.12	0.09	-0.16	0.24	1	4252.45	3760.40
ind_FRic[25]	0.01	0.00	0.12	0.09	-0.19	0.20	1	4719.22	3973.27
ind_FRic[26]	0.00	0.00	0.12	0.09	-0.19	0.20	1	4392.33	3723.46
ind_FRic[27]	0.00	0.00	0.12	0.09	-0.19	0.21	1	4037.32	3644.16
ind_FRic[28]	0.01	0.00	0.12	0.09	-0.18	0.20	1	4791.62	3893.97
ind_FRic[29]	0.01	0.00	0.12	0.09	-0.18	0.21	1	4452.36	4084.55

S4.4 Conditional effects

S4.4.1 Tree height

```
post_FRic <- mod_FRic$draws(sum_FRic[indx_pars, ]$variable, format = 'df')
post_FRic <- post_FRic[, sum_FRic[indx_pars, ]$variable]

conditional_effect_FRic <-
  function(par, x_var, N = 500, FRic = T) {

    x <- seq(min(x_var), max(x_var), length.out = N)

    ind_FRic <- grep('^ind_FRic', colnames(post_FRic))
    ind_S <- grep('^ind_S', colnames(post_FRic))

    est <-
      lapply(x, FUN =
        function(i) {
          if (FRic) {
            mu_ <-
              post_FRic$alpha_FRic +
              post_FRic[[par]] * i +
              apply(post_FRic[, ind_FRic], 1, mean)

            mu_pred <-
              rstudent(N, 7, mu_, post_FRic$sigma_FRic)
          } else {
            mu_ <-
              post_FRic$alpha_S +
              post_FRic[[par]] * i +
              apply(post_FRic[, ind_S], 1, mean)

            mu_pred <-
              rstudent(N, 7, mu_, post_FRic$sigma_S)
          }

          tibble(mu = mean(mu_),
                 li = quantile(mu_, 0.025),
                 ls = quantile(mu_, 0.975),
                 li_pred = quantile(mu_pred, 0.025),
```

```

        ls_pred = quantile(mu_pred, 0.975))
    })
  est <- do.call('rbind', est)
  est$x <- x
  est
}

est_height_FRic <- conditional_effect_FRic('beta_height_FRic', dat$height)
est_height_S <- conditional_effect_FRic('beta_height_S', dat$height)

plot_cond_heigth_FRic <-
  ggplot() +
  geom_ribbon(data = est_height_FRic,
            aes(x, mu, ymin = li_pred, ymax = ls_pred),
            alpha = 0.5, fill = 'lightblue2') +
  geom_ribbon(data = est_height_FRic,
            aes(x, mu, ymin = li, ymax = ls),
            alpha = 0.7, fill = 'lightblue') +
  geom_line(data = est_height_FRic,
           aes(x, mu), color = 'tan1', linewidth = 1, alpha = 0.7) +
  geom_point(data = tibble(x = dat$height,
                          y = dat$fric),
            aes(x, y), color = 'tan1', alpha = 0.5) +
  theme_classic() +
  labs(x = 'Tree height (z-scores)',
       y = 'FRic (z-scores)') +
  theme(legend.position = c(0.2, 0.9),
        legend.title = element_blank(),
        panel.grid = element_blank(),
        axis.line = element_line(linewidth = 0.25))

plot_cond_heigth_S <-
  ggplot() +
  geom_ribbon(data = est_height_S,
            aes(x, mu, ymin = li_pred, ymax = ls_pred),
            alpha = 0.5, fill = 'lightblue2') +
  geom_ribbon(data = est_height_S,
            aes(x, mu, ymin = li, ymax = ls),
            alpha = 0.7, fill = 'lightblue') +
  geom_line(data = est_height_S,

```

```

    aes(x, mu), color = 'tan1', linewidth = 1, alpha = 0.7) +
geom_point(data = tibble(x = dat$height,
                          y = dat$s_std),
           aes(x, y), color = 'tan1', alpha = 0.5) +
theme_classic() +
labs(x = 'Tree height (z-scores)',
     y = 'S (z-scores)') +
theme(legend.position = c(0.2, 0.9),
      legend.title = element_blank(),
      panel.grid = element_blank(),
      axis.line = element_line(linewidth = 0.25))

```

S4.4.2 Urbanisation

```

est_urban_FRic <- conditional_effect_FRic('beta_urban_FRic',
                                         dat$infrastructure)
est_urban_S <- conditional_effect_FRic('beta_urban_S', dat$infrastructure)

plot_cond_urban_FRic <-
  ggplot() +
  geom_ribbon(data = est_urban_FRic,
            aes(x, mu, ymin = li_pred, ymax = ls_pred),
            alpha = 0.5, fill = 'lightblue2') +
  geom_ribbon(data = est_urban_FRic,
            aes(x, mu, ymin = li, ymax = ls),
            alpha = 0.7, fill = 'lightblue') +
  geom_line(data = est_urban_FRic,
           aes(x, mu), color = 'tan1', linewidth = 1, alpha = 0.7) +
  geom_point(data = tibble(x = dat$infrastructure,
                           y = dat$fric),
            aes(x, y), color = 'tan1', alpha = 0.5) +
  theme_classic() +
  labs(x = 'Infrastructure cover (z-scores)',
       y = 'FRic (z-scores)') +
  theme(legend.position = c(0.2, 0.9),
        legend.title = element_blank(),
        panel.grid = element_blank(),
        axis.line = element_line(linewidth = 0.25))

plot_cond_urban_S <-

```

```

ggplot() +
  geom_ribbon(data = est_urban_S,
            aes(x, mu, ymin = li_pred, ymax = ls_pred),
            alpha = 0.5, fill = 'lightblue2') +
  geom_ribbon(data = est_urban_S,
            aes(x, mu, ymin = li, ymax = ls),
            alpha = 0.7, fill = 'lightblue') +
  geom_line(data = est_urban_S,
           aes(x, mu), color = 'tan1', linewidth = 1, alpha = 0.7) +
  geom_point(data = tibble(x = dat$infrastructure,
                          y = dat$s_std),
            aes(x, y), color = 'tan1', alpha = 0.5) +
  theme_classic() +
  labs(x = 'Infrastructure cover (z-scores)',
       y = 'S (z-scores)') +
  theme(legend.position = c(0.2, 0.9),
        legend.title = element_blank(),
        panel.grid = element_blank(),
        axis.line = element_line(linewidth = 0.25))

```

S4.4.3 Tree cover

```

est_forest_FRic <- conditional_effect_FRic('beta_forest_FRic', dat$tree)
est_forest_S <- conditional_effect_FRic('beta_forest_S', dat$tree)

plot_cond_forest_FRic <-
  ggplot() +
  geom_ribbon(data = est_forest_FRic,
            aes(x, mu, ymin = li_pred, ymax = ls_pred),
            alpha = 0.5, fill = 'lightblue2') +
  geom_ribbon(data = est_forest_FRic,
            aes(x, mu, ymin = li, ymax = ls),
            alpha = 0.7, fill = 'lightblue') +
  geom_line(data = est_forest_FRic,
           aes(x, mu), color = 'tan1', linewidth = 1, alpha = 0.7) +
  geom_point(data = tibble(x = dat$tree,
                          y = dat$fric),
            aes(x, y), color = 'tan1', alpha = 0.5) +
  theme_classic() +
  labs(x = 'Tree cover (z-scores)',

```

```

    y = 'FRic (z-scores)') +
  theme(legend.position = c(0.2, 0.9),
        legend.title = element_blank(),
        panel.grid = element_blank(),
        axis.line = element_line(linewidth = 0.25))

plot_cond_forest_S <-
  ggplot() +
  geom_ribbon(data = est_forest_S,
            aes(x, mu, ymin = li_pred, ymax = ls_pred),
            alpha = 0.5, fill = 'lightblue2') +
  geom_ribbon(data = est_forest_S,
            aes(x, mu, ymin = li, ymax = ls),
            alpha = 0.7, fill = 'lightblue') +
  geom_line(data = est_forest_S,
           aes(x, mu), color = 'tan1', linewidth = 1, alpha = 0.7) +
  geom_point(data = tibble(x = dat$infrastructure,
                          y = dat$s_std),
            aes(x, y), color = 'tan1', alpha = 0.5) +
  theme_classic() +
  labs(x = 'Tree cover (z-scores)',
       y = 'S (z-scores)') +
  theme(legend.position = c(0.2, 0.9),
        legend.title = element_blank(),
        panel.grid = element_blank(),
        axis.line = element_line(linewidth = 0.25))

```

S4.5 Causal effect

S4.5.1 Height

```

causal_effect_FRic <-
  function(par_EQ1, par_EQ2, x_var, x_label, total_effect = T, negative = F) {
    ind_s <- grep('^ind_S', colnames(post_FRic))
    ind_FRic <- grep('^ind_FRic', colnames(post_FRic))
    mu_S <- mean(d$$S)
    SD_S <- sd(d$$S)

    mu_FRic <- mean(d$fric_obs_22)
    SD_FRic <- sd(d$fric_obs_22)
  }

```

```

estimated <-
  lapply(c(min, max), FUN =
    function(.fun) {

      est_S <-
        post_FRic$alpha_S +
        post_FRic[[par_EQ1]] * .fun(x_var) +
        apply(post_FRic[, ind_s], 1, mean)

      if (total_effect) {
        message('Calculating total effect')
      } else {
        message('Calculating conditional effect')
        est_S <- min(dat$s_std)
      }

      est_FRic <-
        post_FRic$alpha_FRic +
        post_FRic$beta_S * est_S +
        post_FRic[[par_EQ2]] * .fun(x_var) +
        apply(post_FRic[, ind_FRic], 1, mean)

      est_FRic <- mu_FRic + est_FRic * SD_FRic
      est_S <- mu_S + est_S * SD_S

      list(S = tibble(est = est_S,
                      Y = 'S',
                      X = x_label),
           FRic = tibble(est = est_FRic,
                         Y = 'FRic',
                         X = x_label))

    })

names(estimated) <- c('Min', 'Max')

estimated <-
  lapply(names(estimated), FUN =
    function(x) {
      d <- estimated[[x]]
      d$$intervention <- x
      d$FRic$intervention <- x
    })

```

```

      d
    })
names(estimated) <- c('Min', 'Max')

estimated <-
  lapply(estimated, FUN =
    function(x) {
      do.call('rbind', x)
    })
estimated <- do.call('rbind', estimated)
estimated <- split(estimated, estimated$Y)
lapply(estimated, FUN =
  function(x) {

    if (negative) {
      x2 <- x[x$intervention == 'Max', ]
      x2$est <-
        x[x$intervention == 'Min', ]$est -
        x[x$intervention == 'Max', ]$est

      x2$intervention <- 'Contrast'
      z <- (x2$est * 100)/x[x$intervention == 'Min', ]$est
      x$porcentaje <- NA
      x2$porcentaje <- z
      x2 <- rbind(x, x2)
      x2$intervention <- as.factor(x2$intervention)
      x2$intervention <- factor(x2$intervention,
                              levels = c('Min', 'Max',
                                           'Contrast'))

      x2
    } else {
      x2 <- x[x$intervention == 'Max', ]
      x2$est <-
        x[x$intervention == 'Max', ]$est -
        x[x$intervention == 'Min', ]$est

      x2$intervention <- 'Contrast'
      z <- (x2$est * 100)/x[x$intervention == 'Max', ]$est
      x$porcentaje <- NA
      x2$porcentaje <- z
      x2 <- rbind(x, x2)
      x2$intervention <- as.factor(x2$intervention)
    }
  })

```

```

        x2$intervention <- factor(x2$intervention,
                                levels = c('Min', 'Max',
                                             'Contrast'))
      }
    }
  })
}

effect_height <- causal_effect_FRic('beta_height_S',
                                    'beta_height_FRic',
                                    dat$height, 'Height', T, negative = F)

```

Calculating total effect
 Calculating total effect

```

effect_height$FRic$total_effect <- 'Total effect'

conditional_height_FRic <- causal_effect_FRic('beta_height_S',
                                              'beta_height_FRic',
                                              dat$height, 'Height', F,
                                              negative = F)[[1]]

```

Calculating conditional effect

Calculating conditional effect

```

conditional_height_FRic$total_effect <- 'Conditional effect'

plot_CE_height_FRic <-
  rbind(effect_height$FRic,
        conditional_height_FRic) |>
  group_by(intervention, total_effect) |>
  transmute(mu = mean(est),
            li = quantile(est, 0.025),
            ls = quantile(est, 0.975)) |>
  unique() |>
  ggplot() +
  geom_errorbar(aes(intervention, ymin = li, ymax = ls,
                    color = total_effect), width = 0,

```

```

        position = position_dodge(width = 0.3)) +
geom_point(aes(intervention, mu, color = total_effect),
           position = position_dodge(width = 0.3)) +
scale_color_manual(values = c('tan1', 'lightblue')) +
scale_fill_manual(values = c('tan1', 'lightblue')) +
lims(y = c(-25, 50)) +
theme_classic() +
labs(x = 'Intervention of tree height',
     y = 'FRic') +
geom_hline(yintercept = 0, linetype = 3) +
theme(legend.position = c(0.37, 0.15),
      legend.background = element_blank(),
      legend.title = element_blank(),
      panel.grid = element_blank(),
      axis.line = element_line(linewidth = 0.25))

# figure height FRic

plot_heigh_FRic <-
  plot_grid(plot_cond_heigh_S,
            plot_cond_heigh_FRic,
            plot_CE_height_FRic, ncol = 3,
            labels = c('(i)', '(ii)', '(iii)'),
            label_fontface = 'plain',
            label_size = 10,
            label_x = 0.175)

```

S4.5.1.1 Summary causal effect height

```

cont_height_FRic <- na.omit(effect_height$FRic)

conditional_height_FRic <- na.omit(conditional_height_FRic)

diff_height_FRic <- cont_height_FRic$est - conditional_height_FRic$est

knitr::kable(
  tribble(~ value,           ~estimation,
          'P(total effect > 0)', mean(cont_height_FRic$est > 0),
          'mu total effect', mean(cont_height_FRic$est),
          'sd total effect', sd(cont_height_FRic$est),
          'AVG change relative to maximum (total) (%)',

```

```

mean(cont_height_FRic$porcentaje),
'SD change relative to maximum (total) (%)',
sd(cont_height_FRic$porcentaje),
'P(conditional effect > 0)', mean(conditional_height_FRic$est > 0),
'mu conditional effect', mean(conditional_height_FRic$est),
'sd conditional effect', sd(conditional_height_FRic$est),
'AVG change relative to maximum (conditional) (%)',
mean(conditional_height_FRic$porcentaje),
'SD change relative to maximum (conditional) (%)',
sd(conditional_height_FRic$porcentaje),
'P(total > conditional)',
mean(cont_height_FRic$est > conditional_height_FRic$est),
'AVG diff total-conditional (%)',
(100-(mean(diff_height_FRic)*100) / mean(cont_height_FRic$est))),
digits = 2, caption = 'Summary of causal effect'
)

```

Table S2: Summary of causal effect

value	estimation
P(total effect > 0)	0.98
mu total effect	17.72
sd total effect	8.16
AVG change relative to maximum (total) (%)	46.46
SD change relative to maximum (total) (%)	18.17
P(conditional effect > 0)	0.95
mu conditional effect	11.63
sd conditional effect	7.02
AVG change relative to maximum (conditional) (%)	44.04
SD change relative to maximum (conditional) (%)	24.94
P(total > conditional)	0.94
AVG diff total-conditional (%)	65.61

S4.5.2 Urbanization

```

effect_urban <- causal_effect_FRic('beta_urban_S',
                                   'beta_urban_FRic',
                                   dat$infrastructure, 'Urban', T,
                                   negative = T)

```

Calculating total effect
Calculating total effect

```
effect_urban$FRic$total_effect <- 'Total effect'  
  
conditional_urban_FRic <- causal_effect_FRic('beta_urban_S',  
                                             'beta_urban_FRic',  
                                             dat$infrastructure, 'Urban', F,  
                                             negative = T)[[1]]
```

Calculating conditional effect

Calculating conditional effect

```
conditional_urban_FRic$total_effect <- 'Conditional effect'  
  
plot_CE_urban_FRic <-  
  rbind(effect_urban$FRic,  
        conditional_urban_FRic) |>  
  group_by(intervention, total_effect) |>  
  transmute(mu = mean(est),  
            li = quantile(est, 0.025),  
            ls = quantile(est, 0.975)) |>  
  unique() |>  
  ggplot() +  
  geom_errorbar(aes(intervention, ymin = li, ymax = ls,  
                   color = total_effect), width = 0,  
               position = position_dodge(width = 0.3)) +  
  geom_point(aes(intervention, mu, color = total_effect),  
            position = position_dodge(width = 0.3)) +  
  scale_color_manual(values = c('tan1', 'lightblue')) +  
  scale_fill_manual(values = c('tan1', 'lightblue')) +  
  theme_classic() +  
  labs(x = 'Intervention of\n infrastructure cover',  
       y = 'FRic') +  
  lims(y = c(-25, 50)) +  
  geom_hline(yintercept = 0, linetype = 3) +  
  theme(legend.position = 'none',  
        legend.title = element_blank(),  
        panel.grid = element_blank(),  
        axis.line = element_line(linewidth = 0.25))
```

```

# figure urban FRic

plot_urban_FRic <-
  plot_grid(plot_cond_urban_S,
            plot_cond_urban_FRic,
            plot_CE_urban_FRic, ncol = 3,
            labels = c('(i)', '(ii)', '(iii)'),
            label_fontface = 'plain',
            label_size = 10,
            label_x = 0.175)

```

S4.5.2.1 Summary causal effect urbanization

```

cont_urban_FRic <- na.omit(effect_urban$FRic)

conditional_urban_FRic <- na.omit(conditional_urban_FRic)

diff_urban_FRic <- cont_urban_FRic$est - conditional_urban_FRic$est

knitr::kable(tribble(~ value, ~estimation,
  'P(total effect < 0)', mean(cont_urban_FRic$est > 0),
  'mu total effect', mean(cont_urban_FRic$est),
  'sd total effect', sd(cont_urban_FRic$est),
  'AVG change relative to maximum (total) (%)',
  mean(cont_urban_FRic$porcentaje),
  'SD change relative to maximum (total) (%)',
  sd(cont_urban_FRic$porcentaje),
  'P(conditional effect > 0)', mean(conditional_urban_FRic$est > 0),
  'mu conditional effect', mean(conditional_urban_FRic$est),
  'sd conditional effect', sd(conditional_urban_FRic$est),
  'AVG change relative to maximum (conditional) (%)',
  mean(conditional_urban_FRic$porcentaje),
  'SD change relative to maximum (conditional) (%)',
  sd(conditional_urban_FRic$porcentaje),
  'P(total < conditional)',
  mean(cont_urban_FRic$est > conditional_urban_FRic$est),
  'AVG diff total-conditional (%)',
  (mean(diff_urban_FRic)*100 / mean(cont_urban_FRic$est)-100)),
  digits = 2, caption = 'Summary of causal effect'
)

```

Table S3: Summary of causal effect

value	estimation
P(total effect < 0)	0.87
mu total effect	7.40
sd total effect	6.78
AVG change relative to maximum (total) (%)	24.03
SD change relative to maximum (total) (%)	22.32
P(conditional effect > 0)	0.70
mu conditional effect	3.09
sd conditional effect	6.01
AVG change relative to maximum (conditional) (%)	11.57
SD change relative to maximum (conditional) (%)	34.98
P(total < conditional)	0.90
AVG diff total-conditional (%)	-41.68

S4.5.3 Tree cover

```
effect_forest <- causal_effect_FRic('beta_forest_S',
                                   'beta_forest_FRic',
                                   dat$tree, 'forest', T, negative = T)
```

Calculating total effect
Calculating total effect

```
effect_forest$FRic$total_effect <- 'Total effect'

conditional_forest_FRic <- causal_effect_FRic('beta_forest_S',
                                              'beta_forest_FRic',
                                              dat$tree, 'forest', F,
                                              negative = T)[[1]]
```

Calculating conditional effect

Calculating conditional effect

```

conditional_forest_FRic$total_effect <- 'Conditional effect'

plot_CE_forest_FRic <-
  rbind(effect_forest$FRic,
        conditional_forest_FRic) |>
  group_by(intervention, total_effect) |>
  transmute(mu = mean(est),
            li = quantile(est, 0.025),
            ls = quantile(est, 0.975)) |>
  unique() |>
  ggplot() +
  geom_errorbar(aes(intervention, ymin = li, ymax = ls,
                   color = total_effect), width = 0,
               position = position_dodge(width = 0.3)) +
  geom_point(aes(intervention, mu, color = total_effect),
             position = position_dodge(width = 0.3)) +
  scale_color_manual(values = c('tan1', 'lightblue')) +
  scale_fill_manual(values = c('tan1', 'lightblue')) +
  lims(y = c(-25, 50)) +
  theme_classic() +
  labs(x = 'Intervention of\n tree cover',
       y = 'FRic') +
  geom_hline(yintercept = 0, linetype = 3) +
  theme(legend.position = 'none',
        legend.title = element_blank(),
        panel.grid = element_blank(),
        axis.line = element_line(linewidth = 0.25))

# figure forest FRic

plot_forest_FRic <-
  plot_grid(plot_cond_forest_S,
            plot_cond_forest_FRic,
            plot_CE_forest_FRic, ncol = 3,
            labels = c('(i)', '(ii)', '(iii)'),
            label_fontface = 'plain',
            label_size = 10,
            label_x = 0.175)

```

S4.5.3.1 Summary causal effect tree cover

```

cont_forest_FRic <- na.omit(effect_forest$FRic)

conditional_forest_FRic <- na.omit(conditional_forest_FRic)

diff_forest_FRic <- cont_forest_FRic$est - conditional_forest_FRic$est

knitr::kable(
  tribble(~value, ~estimation,
    'P(total effect < 0)', mean(cont_forest_FRic$est > 0),
    'mu total effect', mean(cont_forest_FRic$est),
    'sd total effect', sd(cont_forest_FRic$est),
    'AVG change relative to maximum (total) (%)',
    mean(cont_forest_FRic$porcentaje),
    'SD change relative to maximum (total) (%)',
    sd(cont_forest_FRic$porcentaje),
    'P(conditional effect > 0)', mean(conditional_forest_FRic$est > 0),
    'mu conditional effect', mean(conditional_forest_FRic$est),
    'sd conditional effect', sd(conditional_forest_FRic$est),
    'AVG change relative to maximum (conditional) (%)',
    median(conditional_forest_FRic$porcentaje),
    'SD change relative to maximum (conditional) (%)',
    sd(conditional_forest_FRic$porcentaje),
    'P(total < conditional)',
    mean(cont_forest_FRic$est > conditional_forest_FRic$est),
    'AVG diff total-conditional (%)',
    (mean(diff_forest_FRic)*100 / mean(cont_forest_FRic$est))), digits = 2,
  caption = 'Summary of causal effect'
)

```

Table S4: Summary of causal effect

value	estimation
P(total effect < 0)	0.80
mu total effect	6.44
sd total effect	7.70
AVG change relative to maximum (total) (%)	20.12
SD change relative to maximum (total) (%)	25.74
P(conditional effect > 0)	0.80
mu conditional effect	5.53
sd conditional effect	6.63
AVG change relative to maximum (conditional) (%)	28.38

value	estimation
SD change relative to maximum (conditional) (%)	34.57
P(total < conditional)	0.61
AVG diff total-conditional (%)	14.15

5 Section 5: Figure 2

Code reproducing the figure in the main document.

```
plot_grid(plot_heigh_FRic,  
          plot_urban_FRic,  
          plot_forest_FRic,  
          ncol = 1,  
          labels = c('(a)', '(b)', '(c)'),  
          label_size = 12,  
          label_fontface = 'plain',  
          label_x = -0.007)
```


Figure S5: Intrinsic (a) and extrinsic (b, c) drivers influencing the functional richness (FRic) and species richness (S) of birds foraging on an *S. terebinthifolia* population. Effects on S (a-i to c-i iii) imply indirect effects (i.e., $X \rightarrow S \rightarrow \text{FRic}$) on FRic, whereas effects on FRic (a-ii to c-ii) denote direct effects (a i-ii, b i-ii and c i-ii). The dots indicate observed values, the solid line is the average estimation, the inner bands include 95% CI of the estimation, and the outer bands show 95% CI of the prediction. Error bars and dots in a-iii, b-iii, and c-iii show 95% credibility intervals and average values of the causal effect of intervening factors to minimum and maximum values; the contrast shows the difference between such interventions. The total effect implies both direct and indirect effects of driver i on FRic. In contrast, the conditional effect denotes the direct effect of driver i on FRic while holding S on the minimum value.

6 Section 6: Model FDiv

Formatting the data frame in a list object.

```
dat2 <- dat_1

indx_na_FDiv <- dat2$ind_id[which(is.na(dat2$fdiv_obs_22))]

dist_inds_FDiv <- dist_inds[-indx_na_FDiv, -indx_na_FDiv]

dat2 <- dat2[-indx_na_FDiv ,]

dat2$ind_id <- 1:nrow(dat2)

colnames(dist_inds_FDiv) <- paste0('Ind', dat2$ind_id)
rownames(dist_inds_FDiv) <- paste0('Ind', dat2$ind_id)

dat2 <- lapply(dat2, function(x) x)

dat2$N <- length(dat2$ind_id)
dat2$N_ind <- max(dat2$ind_id)
dat2$dist_mat <- dist_inds_FDiv
names(dat2)[2:4] <- c('fric', 'fdiv', 'freg')
dat2$fdiv <- as.vector(scale(log(dat2$fdiv)))
```

S6.1 Stan code

```
cat(file = 'model_FDiv.stan',
    '\n\n',
    'functions {\n',
    '  matrix cov_GPL2(matrix x,\n',
    '                  real eta,\n',
    '                  real rho,\n',
    '                  real delta) {\n\n',
    '    int N = dims(x)[1];\n',
    '    matrix[N, N] K;\n',
    '    matrix[N, N] L_K;\n\n',
    '    for (i in 1:(N-1)) {\n
```

```

        K[i, i] = eta + delta;
        for (j in (i+1):N) {
            K[i, j] = eta * exp(-rho * square(x[i, j]));
            K[j, i] = K[i, j];
        }
    }

    K[N, N] = eta + delta;
    L_K = cholesky_decompose(K);
    return L_K;
}

}

data {
    int N;
    int N_ind;
    matrix[N_ind, N_ind] dist_mat;
    array[N] int ind_id;
    vector[N] fdiv;
    vector[N] s_std;
    vector[N] height;
    vector[N] crop;
    vector[N] duration;
    vector[N] fruit;
    vector[N] tree;
    vector[N] infrastructure;
}

parameters {

    // model S
    real alpha_S;
    real<lower = 0> sigma_S;
    real beta_forest_S;
    real beta_height_S;
    real beta_crop_S;
    real beta_duration_S;
    real beta_fruit_S;
    real beta_urban_S;
    vector[N_ind] z_ind_S;
    real<lower = 0> eta_S;
    real<lower = 0> rho_S;
}

```

```

// model FDiv
real alpha_FDiv;
real<lower = 0> sigma_FDiv;
real beta_S;
real beta_forest_FDiv;
real beta_height_FDiv;
real beta_crop_FDiv;
real beta_duration_FDiv;
real beta_fruit_FDiv;
real beta_urban_FDiv;
vector[N_ind] z_ind_FDiv;
real<lower = 0> eta_FDiv;
real<lower = 0> rho_FDiv;
}

transformed parameters {
  // pars S
  vector[N_ind] ind_S;
  matrix[N_ind, N_ind] L_K_S;
  L_K_S = cov_GPL2(dist_mat, eta_S, rho_S, 0.001);
  ind_S = L_K_S * z_ind_S;

  // pars FDiv
  vector[N_ind] ind_FDiv;
  matrix[N_ind, N_ind] L_K_FDiv;
  L_K_FDiv = cov_GPL2(dist_mat, eta_FDiv, rho_FDiv, 0.001);
  ind_FDiv = L_K_FDiv * z_ind_FDiv;
}

model {

  // prior S
  alpha_S ~ normal(0, 1);
  sigma_S ~ exponential(1);
  z_ind_S ~ normal(0, 0.25);
  eta_S ~ exponential(4);
  rho_S ~ exponential(1);
  beta_forest_S ~ normal(0, 0.25);
  beta_height_S ~ normal(0, 0.25);
  beta_crop_S ~ normal(0, 0.25);
  beta_duration_S ~ normal(0, 0.25);
  beta_fruit_S ~ normal(0, 0.25);
}

```

```

beta_urban_S ~ normal(0, 0.25);

// prior FDiv
alpha_FDiv ~ normal(0, 1);
sigma_FDiv ~ exponential(1);
z_ind_FDiv ~ normal(0, 0.25);
eta_FDiv ~ exponential(4);
rho_FDiv ~ exponential(1);
beta_forest_FDiv ~ normal(0, 0.25);
beta_height_FDiv ~ normal(0, 0.25);
beta_crop_FDiv ~ normal(0, 0.25);
beta_duration_FDiv ~ normal(0, 0.25);
beta_fruit_FDiv ~ normal(0, 0.25);
beta_urban_FDiv ~ normal(0, 0.25);
beta_S ~ normal(0, 1);

// model S
s_std ~ student_t(7,
                  alpha_S +
                  beta_forest_S * tree +
                  beta_height_S * height +
                  beta_crop_S * crop +
                  beta_duration_S * duration +
                  beta_fruit_S * fruit +
                  beta_urban_S * infrastructure +
                  ind_S[ind_id], sigma_S);

// model FDiv
fdiv ~ student_t(7,
                 alpha_FDiv +
                 beta_S * s_std +
                 beta_forest_FDiv * tree +
                 beta_height_FDiv * height +
                 beta_crop_FDiv * crop +
                 beta_duration_FDiv * duration +
                 beta_fruit_FDiv * fruit +
                 beta_urban_FDiv * infrastructure +
                 ind_FDiv[ind_id], sigma_FDiv);
}

generated quantities {
  array[N] real ppcheck_S;

```

```

array[N] real ppcheck_FDiv;
vector[N] mu_S;
vector[N] mu_FDiv;

mu_S = alpha_S +
      beta_forest_S * tree +
      beta_height_S * height +
      beta_crop_S * crop +
      beta_duration_S * duration +
      beta_fruit_S * fruit +
      beta_urban_S * infrastructure +
      ind_S[ind_id];

ppcheck_S = student_t_rng(7, mu_S, sigma_S);

mu_FDiv = alpha_FDiv +
          beta_S * s_std +
          beta_forest_FDiv * tree +
          beta_height_FDiv * height +
          beta_crop_FDiv * crop +
          beta_duration_FDiv * duration +
          beta_fruit_FDiv * fruit +
          beta_urban_FDiv * infrastructure +
          ind_FDiv[ind_id];

ppcheck_FDiv = student_t_rng(7, mu_FDiv, sigma_FDiv);

}
')
```

S6.2 Fitting the model

```

file <- paste0(getwd(), '/model_FDiv.stan')
fit_FDiv <- cmdstan_model(file, compile = T)

indx_na_vars <-
  unlist(lapply(dat2, function(x) sum(is.na(x)) == 0),
        use.names = F)
```

```
mod_FDiv <-  
  fit_FDiv$sample(  
    data = dat2[indx_na_vars],  
    iter_warmup = 500,  
    iter_sampling = 4e3,  
    chains = 3,  
    parallel_chains = 3,  
    thin = 3,  
    seed = 5  
  )
```

S6.3 Model diagnostics

```
sum_FDiv <- mod_FDiv$summary()  
  
mod_diagnostics(mod_FDiv, sum_FDiv)
```


Figure S6: Rhat values vs effective sampling size (ess). Rhat < 1.05 indicates that the Markov Chains converged to the same stationary distribution. ess must be at least 100 in order to be reliable

```

indx_pars <-
  c(grep('^beta', sum_FDiv$variable),
    grep('^sigma', sum_FDiv$variable),
    grep('^alpha', sum_FDiv$variable),
    grep('^ind', sum_FDiv$variable))

par(mfrow = c(4, 5), mar = c(4, 4, 1, 1))
for (i in 1:17) {
  trace_plot(mod_FDiv, sum_FDiv$variable[indx_pars[i]], 3)
}
par(mfrow = c(1, 1))

```


Figure S7: Trace plots showing chain convergence per parameter

```

ppcheck_S <- mod_FDiv$draws('ppcheck_S', format = 'matrix')
ppcheck_FDiv <- mod_FDiv$draws('ppcheck_FDiv', format = 'matrix')

par(mfrow = c(1, 2), mar = c(4, 4, 1, 1))
plot(density(dat2$s_std), xlim = c(-4, 5),
      ylim = c(0, 0.7), main = '', xlab = 'N species (z-scores)')
for (i in 1:500) lines(density(ppcheck_S[i, ]), lwd = 0.1)
lines(density(dat2$s_std), col = 'red', lwd = 1.5)

```

```

plot(density(dat2$fdiv), xlim = c(-4, 5),
     ylim = c(0, 0.7), main = '', xlab = 'FDiv (z-scores)')
for (i in 1:500) lines(density(ppcheck_FDiv[i, ]), lwd = 0.1)
lines(density(dat2$fdiv), col = 'red', lwd = 1.5)

```


Figure S8: Posterior predictive checks of the model describing species richness and FDiv of the birds assemblage

```

par(mfrow = c(1, 1))

```

```

par(mfrow = c(2, 2))
plot(density(apply(ppcheck_S, 1, mean)), xlab = 'AVG. S (estimated)',
     main = '')
abline(v = mean(dat2$s_std), col = 'red')
plot(density(apply(ppcheck_S, 1, sd)), xlab = 'SD. S (estimated)',
     main = '')
abline(v = sd(dat2$s_std), col = 'red')

plot(density(apply(ppcheck_FDiv, 1, mean)), xlab = 'AVG. FDiv (estimated)',
     main = '')
abline(v = mean(dat2$fdiv), col = 'red')

```

```
plot(density(apply(ppcheck_FDiv, 1, sd)), xlab = 'SD. FDiv (estimated)',
     main = '')
abline(v = sd(dat2$fdiv), col = 'red')
```


Figure S9: Observed average and SD from species richness and FDiv against the estimated by the model

```
par(mfrow = c(1, 1))
```

```
indx_pars <-
  c(grep('^beta', sum_FDiv$variable),
    grep('^sigma', sum_FDiv$variable),
    grep('^alpha', sum_FDiv$variable),
    grep('^ind', sum_FDiv$variable))
```

```
text <- 'Average, SD, confidence intervals and metrics of
sampling diagnostics for the parameters estimating
species richness and FDiv of the birds assemblage'
```

```
knitr::kable(
  sum_FDiv[indx_pars, ],
  digits = 2,
```

```
caption = text
)
```

Table S5: Average, SD, confidence intervals and metrics of sampling diagnostics for the parameters estimating species richness and FDiv of the birds assemblage

variable	mean	median	sd	mad	q5	q95	rhat	ess_bulk	ess_tail
beta_forest_S	0.03	0.03	0.16	0.15	-0.23	0.29	1	4303.02	3645.91
beta_height_S	0.11	0.11	0.16	0.16	-0.16	0.39	1	4281.27	3643.19
beta_crop_S	0.14	0.14	0.16	0.15	-0.10	0.41	1	4662.87	3916.64
beta_duration_S	0.19	0.19	0.17	0.17	-0.10	0.46	1	4199.02	3728.39
beta_fruit_S	0.10	0.10	0.17	0.17	-0.16	0.39	1	4350.17	3787.48
beta_urban_S	-0.25	-0.25	0.14	0.14	-0.48	-0.01	1	4423.96	3993.49
beta_S	0.20	0.20	0.16	0.15	-0.05	0.47	1	4024.45	3774.71
beta_forest_FDiv	0.02	0.02	0.14	0.14	-0.21	0.25	1	4484.55	3971.11
beta_height_FDiv	0.12	0.12	0.13	0.13	-0.10	0.34	1	4451.25	3489.77
beta_crop_FDiv	0.19	0.20	0.16	0.15	-0.08	0.43	1	4256.69	3855.58
beta_duration_FDiv	0.01	0.01	0.14	0.14	-0.22	0.23	1	3864.42	3778.90
beta_fruit_FDiv	-0.07	-0.07	0.13	0.12	-0.29	0.14	1	4294.15	3674.67
beta_urban_FDiv	-0.22	-0.22	0.13	0.12	-0.42	-0.01	1	3986.54	3138.88
sigma_S	0.71	0.70	0.14	0.13	0.51	0.95	1	4356.86	3754.72
sigma_FDiv	0.52	0.50	0.12	0.11	0.36	0.73	1	3959.56	3853.22
alpha_S	0.09	0.09	0.16	0.16	-0.17	0.36	1	4402.96	3737.63
alpha_FDiv	-0.18	-0.19	0.12	0.12	-0.37	0.03	1	4168.50	3894.31
ind_S[1]	-0.02	-0.01	0.13	0.09	-0.24	0.19	1	4268.05	3803.90
ind_S[2]	-0.02	-0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.24	0.16	1	5068.75	3985.06
ind_S[3]	-0.01	-0.01	0.13	0.09	-0.23	0.18	1	4444.95	3708.49
ind_S[4]	0.01	0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.17	0.22	1	4203.62	3726.38
ind_S[5]	-0.01	0.00	0.13	0.09	-0.21	0.19	1	4619.80	3563.71
ind_S[6]	0.02	0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.16	0.25	1	4693.64	4003.84
ind_S[7]	-0.01	0.00	0.12	0.09	-0.21	0.19	1	4646.02	3903.91
ind_S[8]	-0.02	-0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.23	0.16	1	4598.53	3802.50
ind_S[9]	0.00	0.00	0.12	0.09	-0.20	0.21	1	4510.08	3915.34
ind_S[10]	0.01	0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.17	0.23	1	4791.20	3964.01
ind_S[11]	0.03	0.02	0.13	0.09	-0.16	0.26	1	4144.12	3953.87
ind_S[12]	0.01	0.00	0.12	0.09	-0.19	0.21	1	4647.93	3729.98
ind_S[13]	-0.01	0.00	0.12	0.09	-0.22	0.19	1	4545.14	3814.95
ind_S[14]	0.00	0.00	0.12	0.09	-0.20	0.19	1	4451.19	3522.73
ind_S[15]	0.03	0.02	0.13	0.09	-0.16	0.25	1	4594.09	4064.06
ind_S[16]	-0.02	-0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.24	0.18	1	4733.84	3827.76
ind_S[17]	-0.02	-0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.24	0.17	1	4594.36	3450.96

variable	mean	median	sd	mad	q5	q95	rhat	ess_bulk	ess_tail
ind_S[18]	0.03	0.02	0.13	0.09	-0.15	0.25	1	4121.87	3638.30
ind_S[19]	-0.02	-0.01	0.13	0.10	-0.24	0.17	1	4185.40	3876.75
ind_S[20]	0.01	0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.18	0.22	1	4673.27	3811.46
ind_S[21]	-0.01	0.00	0.12	0.09	-0.21	0.19	1	4438.55	3625.45
ind_S[22]	0.00	0.00	0.12	0.09	-0.20	0.20	1	4676.40	3974.24
ind_S[23]	-0.02	-0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.24	0.16	1	4161.16	3574.66
ind_S[24]	0.00	0.00	0.12	0.09	-0.20	0.20	1	4353.19	3694.06
ind_S[25]	0.01	0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.19	0.22	1	4381.24	3940.94
ind_S[26]	0.02	0.01	0.13	0.09	-0.18	0.24	1	4595.81	3739.69
ind_FDiv[1]	-0.01	0.00	0.11	0.08	-0.19	0.17	1	4660.60	3675.77
ind_FDiv[2]	0.03	0.02	0.12	0.08	-0.13	0.26	1	4612.77	3933.55
ind_FDiv[3]	-0.01	-0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.21	0.17	1	4846.97	3893.18
ind_FDiv[4]	0.02	0.01	0.11	0.08	-0.16	0.21	1	5013.36	3933.81
ind_FDiv[5]	-0.03	-0.02	0.12	0.09	-0.25	0.14	1	4434.58	3385.47
ind_FDiv[6]	-0.01	-0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.21	0.17	1	4405.63	3741.55
ind_FDiv[7]	-0.01	-0.01	0.11	0.08	-0.20	0.17	1	4405.98	3892.60
ind_FDiv[8]	-0.03	-0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.24	0.15	1	4606.74	4013.25
ind_FDiv[9]	0.00	0.00	0.12	0.08	-0.19	0.19	1	4410.66	3730.64
ind_FDiv[10]	0.00	0.00	0.11	0.08	-0.19	0.18	1	4613.75	3749.28
ind_FDiv[11]	-0.01	0.00	0.11	0.08	-0.21	0.17	1	4152.85	3879.87
ind_FDiv[12]	0.03	0.02	0.12	0.08	-0.16	0.24	1	4194.64	3831.71
ind_FDiv[13]	-0.03	-0.02	0.12	0.09	-0.23	0.14	1	4526.58	3882.37
ind_FDiv[14]	0.01	0.00	0.11	0.08	-0.17	0.20	1	4506.55	3933.76
ind_FDiv[15]	-0.01	0.00	0.11	0.08	-0.19	0.17	1	4687.32	3910.25
ind_FDiv[16]	0.01	0.00	0.12	0.09	-0.19	0.20	1	4290.41	4014.30
ind_FDiv[17]	0.02	0.02	0.12	0.09	-0.16	0.22	1	4569.40	3804.47
ind_FDiv[18]	0.00	0.00	0.11	0.08	-0.18	0.18	1	4769.44	3467.88
ind_FDiv[19]	0.00	0.00	0.12	0.09	-0.19	0.20	1	4585.48	3643.97
ind_FDiv[20]	-0.01	-0.01	0.11	0.08	-0.20	0.17	1	4602.65	3590.14
ind_FDiv[21]	0.03	0.02	0.12	0.08	-0.14	0.24	1	4422.86	3668.60
ind_FDiv[22]	0.01	0.00	0.11	0.09	-0.17	0.19	1	4431.21	3959.98
ind_FDiv[23]	-0.02	-0.01	0.11	0.08	-0.21	0.15	1	4368.13	3826.07
ind_FDiv[24]	0.00	0.00	0.11	0.08	-0.18	0.18	1	4684.98	3532.03
ind_FDiv[25]	0.01	0.00	0.12	0.08	-0.17	0.20	1	4677.13	3767.46
ind_FDiv[26]	0.02	0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.16	0.22	1	4858.00	3833.02

S6.4 Conditional effects

S6.4.1 Tree height

```
post_FDiv <- mod_FDiv$draws(sum_FDiv[indx_pars, ]$variable, format = 'df')

post_FDiv <- post_FDiv[, sum_FDiv[indx_pars, ]$variable]

conditional_effect_FDiv <-
  function(par, x_var, N = 500, FDiv = T) {

    x <- seq(min(x_var), max(x_var), length.out = N)

    ind_FDiv <- grep('^ind_FDiv', colnames(post_FDiv))
    ind_S <- grep('^ind_S', colnames(post_FDiv))

    est <-
      lapply(x, FUN =
        function(i) {
          if (FDiv) {
            mu_ <-
              post_FDiv$alpha_FDiv +
              post_FDiv[[par]] * i +
              apply(post_FDiv[, ind_FDiv], 1, mean)

            mu_pred <-
              rstudent(N, 7, mu_, post_FDiv$sigma_FDiv)
          } else {
            mu_ <-
              post_FDiv$alpha_S +
              post_FDiv[[par]] * i +
              apply(post_FDiv[, ind_S], 1, mean)

            mu_pred <-
              rstudent(N, 7, mu_, post_FDiv$sigma_S)
          }

          tibble(mu = mean(mu_),
                 li = quantile(mu_, 0.025),
                 ls = quantile(mu_, 0.975),
                 li_pred = quantile(mu_pred, 0.025),
```

```

        ls_pred = quantile(mu_pred, 0.975))
    })
  est <- do.call('rbind', est)
  est$x <- x
  est
}

est_height_FDiv <- conditional_effect_FDiv('beta_height_FDiv',
                                          dat2$height, FDiv = T)
est_height_S_FDiv <- conditional_effect_FDiv('beta_height_S',
                                             dat2$height, FDiv = F)

plot_cond_heighth_FDiv <-
  ggplot() +
  geom_ribbon(data = est_height_FDiv,
            aes(x, mu, ymin = li_pred, ymax = ls_pred),
            alpha = 0.5, fill = 'lightblue2') +
  geom_ribbon(data = est_height_FDiv,
            aes(x, mu, ymin = li, ymax = ls),
            alpha = 0.7, fill = 'lightblue') +
  geom_line(data = est_height_FDiv,
           aes(x, mu), color = 'tan1', linewidth = 1, alpha = 0.7) +
  geom_point(data = tibble(x = dat2$height,
                          y = dat2$fdiv),
            aes(x, y), color = 'tan1', alpha = 0.5) +
  theme_classic() +
  labs(x = 'Tree height (z-scores)',
       y = 'FDiv (z-scores)') +
  theme(legend.position = c(0.2, 0.9),
        legend.title = element_blank(),
        panel.grid = element_blank(),
        axis.line = element_line(linewidth = 0.25))

plot_cond_heighth_S_FDiv <-
  ggplot() +
  geom_ribbon(data = est_height_S_FDiv,
            aes(x, mu, ymin = li_pred, ymax = ls_pred),
            alpha = 0.5, fill = 'lightblue2') +
  geom_ribbon(data = est_height_S_FDiv,
            aes(x, mu, ymin = li, ymax = ls),

```

```

      alpha = 0.7, fill = 'lightblue') +
geom_line(data = est_height_S_FDiv,
          aes(x, mu), color = 'tan1', linewidth = 1, alpha = 0.7) +
geom_point(data = tibble(x = dat2$height,
                        y = dat2$s_std),
           aes(x, y), color = 'tan1', alpha = 0.5) +
theme_classic() +
labs(x = 'Tree height (z-scores)',
     y = 'S (z-scores)') +
theme(legend.position = c(0.2, 0.9),
      legend.title = element_blank(),
      panel.grid = element_blank(),
      axis.line = element_line(linewidth = 0.25))

```

S6.4.2 Urbanization

```

est_urban_FDiv <- conditional_effect_FDiv('beta_urban_FDiv',
                                       dat2$infrastructure,
                                       FDiv = T)
est_urban_S_FDiv <- conditional_effect_FDiv('beta_urban_S',
                                       dat2$infrastructure,
                                       FDiv = F)

plot_cond_urban_FDiv <-
  ggplot() +
  geom_ribbon(data = est_urban_FDiv,
            aes(x, mu, ymin = li_pred, ymax = ls_pred),
            alpha = 0.5, fill = 'lightblue2') +
  geom_ribbon(data = est_urban_FDiv,
            aes(x, mu, ymin = li, ymax = ls),
            alpha = 0.7, fill = 'lightblue') +
  geom_line(data = est_urban_FDiv,
           aes(x, mu), color = 'tan1', linewidth = 1, alpha = 0.7) +
  geom_point(data = tibble(x = dat2$infrastructure,
                          y = dat2$fdiv),
            aes(x, y), color = 'tan1', alpha = 0.5) +
  theme_classic() +
  labs(x = 'Infrastructure cover (z-scores)',
       y = 'FDiv (z-scores)') +
  theme(legend.position = c(0.2, 0.9),

```

```

    legend.title = element_blank(),
    panel.grid = element_blank(),
    axis.line = element_line(linewidth = 0.25))

plot_cond_urban_S_FDiv <-
  ggplot() +
  geom_ribbon(data = est_urban_S_FDiv,
            aes(x, mu, ymin = li_pred, ymax = ls_pred),
            alpha = 0.5, fill = 'lightblue2') +
  geom_ribbon(data = est_urban_S_FDiv,
            aes(x, mu, ymin = li, ymax = ls),
            alpha = 0.7, fill = 'lightblue') +
  geom_line(data = est_urban_S_FDiv,
           aes(x, mu), color = 'tan1', linewidth = 1, alpha = 0.7) +
  geom_point(data = tibble(x = dat2$infrastructure,
                          y = dat2$s_std),
            aes(x, y), color = 'tan1', alpha = 0.5) +
  theme_classic() +
  labs(x = 'Infrastructure cover (z-scores)',
       y = 'S (z-scores)') +
  theme(legend.position = c(0.2, 0.9),
        legend.title = element_blank(),
        panel.grid = element_blank(),
        axis.line = element_line(linewidth = 0.25))

```

S6.4.3 Crop size

```

est_crop_FDiv <- conditional_effect_FDiv('beta_crop_FDiv',
                                       dat2$crop,
                                       FDiv = T)
est_crop_S_FDiv <- conditional_effect_FDiv('beta_crop_S',
                                       dat2$crop,
                                       FDiv = F)

plot_cond_crop_FDiv <-
  ggplot() +
  geom_ribbon(data = est_crop_FDiv,
            aes(x, mu, ymin = li_pred, ymax = ls_pred),
            alpha = 0.5, fill = 'lightblue2') +
  geom_ribbon(data = est_crop_FDiv,

```

```

        aes(x, mu, ymin = li, ymax = ls),
        alpha = 0.7, fill = 'lightblue') +
geom_line(data = est_crop_FDiv,
          aes(x, mu), color = 'tan1', linewidth = 1, alpha = 0.7) +
geom_point(data = tibble(x = dat2$crop,
                        y = dat2$fdiv),
           aes(x, y), color = 'tan1', alpha = 0.5) +
theme_classic() +
labs(x = 'Crop size (z-scores)',
     y = 'FDiv (z-scores)') +
theme(legend.position = c(0.2, 0.9),
      legend.title = element_blank(),
      panel.grid = element_blank(),
      axis.line = element_line(linewidth = 0.25))

plot_cond_crop_S_FDiv <-
  ggplot() +
  geom_ribbon(data = est_crop_S_FDiv,
            aes(x, mu, ymin = li_pred, ymax = ls_pred),
            alpha = 0.5, fill = 'lightblue2') +
  geom_ribbon(data = est_crop_S_FDiv,
            aes(x, mu, ymin = li, ymax = ls),
            alpha = 0.7, fill = 'lightblue') +
  geom_line(data = est_crop_S_FDiv,
            aes(x, mu), color = 'tan1', linewidth = 1, alpha = 0.7) +
  geom_point(data = tibble(x = dat2$crop,
                          y = dat2$s_std),
            aes(x, y), color = 'tan1', alpha = 0.5) +
  theme_classic() +
  labs(x = 'Crop size (z-scores)',
       y = 'S (z-scores)') +
  theme(legend.position = c(0.2, 0.9),
        legend.title = element_blank(),
        panel.grid = element_blank(),
        axis.line = element_line(linewidth = 0.25))

```

S6.5 Causal effect

S6.5.1 Height

```
causal_effect_FDiv <-  
  function(par_EQ1, par_EQ2, x_var, x_label, total_effect = T, negative = F) {  
    ind_s <- grep('^ind_S', colnames(post_FDiv))  
    ind_FDiv <- grep('^ind_FDiv', colnames(post_FDiv))  
    mu_S <- mean(d$S)  
    SD_S <- sd(d$S)  
  
    FDiv <- dat_1$fdiv_obs_22[-which(is.na(dat_1$fdiv_obs_22))]  
  
    mu_FDiv <- mean(FDiv)  
    SD_FDiv <- sd(FDiv)  
  
    estimated <-  
      lapply(c(min, max), FUN =  
            function(.fun) {  
  
                est_S <-  
                  post_FDiv$alpha_S +  
                  post_FDiv[[par_EQ1]] * .fun(x_var) +  
                  apply(post_FDiv[, ind_s], 1, mean)  
  
                if (total_effect) {  
                  message('Calculating total effect')  
                } else {  
                  message('Calculating conditional effect')  
                  est_S <- min(dat2$s_std)  
                }  
  
                est_FDiv <-  
                  post_FDiv$alpha_FDiv +  
                  post_FDiv$beta_S * est_S +  
                  post_FDiv[[par_EQ2]] * .fun(x_var) +  
                  apply(post_FDiv[, ind_FDiv], 1, mean)  
  
                est_FDiv <- mu_FDiv + est_FDiv * SD_FDiv  
                est_S <- mu_S + est_S * SD_S  
            })  
  }
```

```

        list(S = tibble(est = est_S,
                        Y = 'S',
                        X = x_label),
             FDiv = tibble(est = est_FDiv,
                            Y = 'FDiv',
                            X = x_label))

    })

names(estimated) <- c('Min', 'Max')

estimated <-
  lapply(names(estimated), FUN =
    function(x) {
      d <- estimated[[x]]
      d$$intervention <- x
      d$FDiv$intervention <- x
      d
    })
names(estimated) <- c('Min', 'Max')

estimated <-
  lapply(estimated, FUN =
    function(x) {
      do.call('rbind', x)
    })
estimated <- do.call('rbind', estimated)
estimated <- split(estimated, estimated$Y)
lapply(estimated, FUN =
  function(x) {
    if (negative) {

      x2 <- x[x$intervention == 'Max', ]
      x2$est <-
        x[x$intervention == 'Min', ]$est -
        x[x$intervention == 'Max', ]$est

      x2$intervention <- 'Contrast'
      z <- (x2$est * 100)/x[x$intervention == 'Min', ]$est
      x$porcentaje <- NA
      x2$porcentaje <- z
      x2 <- rbind(x, x2)
    }
  })

```

```

x2$intervention <- as.factor(x2$intervention)
x2$intervention <- factor(x2$intervention,
                          levels = c('Min', 'Max',
                                       'Contrast'))

x2

} else {
x2 <- x[x$intervention == 'Max', ]
x2$est <-
  x[x$intervention == 'Max', ]$est -
  x[x$intervention == 'Min', ]$est

x2$intervention <- 'Contrast'
z <- (x2$est * 100)/x[x$intervention == 'Max', ]$est
x$porcentaje <- NA
x2$porcentaje <- z
x2 <- rbind(x, x2)
x2$intervention <- as.factor(x2$intervention)
x2$intervention <- factor(x2$intervention,
                          levels = c('Min', 'Max',
                                       'Contrast'))

x2
}
})
}

effect_height_FDiv <- causal_effect_FDiv('beta_height_S',
                                         'beta_height_FDiv',
                                         dat2$height, 'Height', T, negative = F)

```

Calculating total effect
Calculating total effect

```

effect_height_FDiv$FDiv$total_effect <- 'Total effect'

conditional_height_FDiv <- causal_effect_FDiv('beta_height_S',
                                              'beta_height_FDiv',
                                              dat$height, 'Height', F,
                                              negative = F)[[1]]

```

Calculating conditional effect

Calculating conditional effect

```
conditional_height_FDiv$total_effect <- 'Conditional effect'

plot_CE_height_FDiv <-
  rbind(effect_height_FDiv$FDiv,
        conditional_height_FDiv) |>
  group_by(intervention, total_effect) |>
  transmute(mu = mean(est),
            li = quantile(est, 0.025),
            ls = quantile(est, 0.975)) |>
  unique() |>
  ggplot() +
  geom_errorbar(aes(intervention, ymin = li, ymax = ls,
                   color = total_effect), width = 0,
               position = position_dodge(width = 0.3)) +
  geom_point(aes(intervention, mu, color = total_effect),
             position = position_dodge(width = 0.3)) +
  scale_color_manual(values = c('tan1', 'lightblue')) +
  scale_fill_manual(values = c('tan1', 'lightblue')) +
  lims(y = c(-1, 2)) +
  theme_classic() +
  labs(x = 'Intervention of tree height',
       y = 'FDiv') +
  geom_hline(yintercept = 0, linetype = 3) +
  theme(legend.position = c(0.37, 0.17),
        legend.background = element_blank(),
        legend.title = element_blank(),
        panel.grid = element_blank(),
        axis.line = element_line(linewidth = 0.25))

# figure height FDiv

plot_heigh_FDiv <-
  plot_grid(plot_cond_heigh_S_FDiv,
            plot_cond_heigh_FDiv,
            plot_CE_height_FDiv, ncol = 3,
            labels = c('(i)', '(ii)', '(iii)'),
            label_fontface = 'plain',
            label_size = 10,
            label_x = 0.175)
```

S6.5.1.1 Summary causal effect height

```

cont_height_FDiv <- na.omit(effect_height_FDiv$FDiv)

conditional_height_FDiv <- na.omit(conditional_height_FDiv)

diff_height_FDiv <- cont_height_FDiv$est - conditional_height_FDiv$est

knitr::kable(
  tribble(~ value,           ~estimation,
    'P(total effect > 0)', mean(cont_height_FDiv$est > 0),
    'mu total effect', mean(cont_height_FDiv$est),
    'sd total effect', sd(cont_height_FDiv$est),
    'AVG change relative to maximum (total) (%)',
    mean(cont_height_FDiv$porcentaje),
    'SD change relative to maximum (total) (%)',
    sd(cont_height_FDiv$porcentaje),
    'P(conditional effect > 0)', mean(conditional_height_FDiv$est > 0),
    'mu conditional effect', mean(conditional_height_FDiv$est),
    'sd conditional effect', sd(conditional_height_FDiv$est),
    'AVG change relative to maximum (conditional) (%)',
    mean(conditional_height_FDiv$porcentaje),
    'SD change relative to maximum (conditional) (%)',
    sd(conditional_height_FDiv$porcentaje),
    'P(total > conditional)',
    mean(cont_height_FDiv$est > conditional_height_FDiv$est),
    'AVG diff total-conditional (%)',
    mean(diff_height_FDiv)*100 / mean(cont_height_FDiv$est)), digits = 2,
  caption = 'Summary of causal effect'
)

```

Table S6: Summary of causal effect

value	estimation
P(total effect > 0)	0.84
mu total effect	0.14
sd total effect	0.14
AVG change relative to maximum (total) (%)	8.68
SD change relative to maximum (total) (%)	8.84
P(conditional effect > 0)	0.81

value	estimation
mu conditional effect	0.13
sd conditional effect	0.15
AVG change relative to maximum (conditional) (%)	8.50
SD change relative to maximum (conditional) (%)	10.08
P(total > conditional)	0.50
AVG diff total-conditional (%)	5.40

S6.5.2 Urbanization

```
effect_urban_FDiv <- causal_effect_FDiv('beta_urban_S',
                                       'beta_urban_FDiv',
                                       dat2$infrastructure,
                                       'Urban', T, negative = F)
```

Calculating total effect

Calculating total effect

```
effect_urban_FDiv$FDiv$total_effect <- 'Total effect'
```

```
conditional_urban_FDiv <- causal_effect_FDiv('beta_urban_S',
                                             'beta_urban_FDiv',
                                             dat2$infrastructure,
                                             'Urban', F, negative = F)[[1]]
```

Calculating conditional effect

Calculating conditional effect

```
conditional_urban_FDiv$total_effect <- 'Conditional effect'
```

```
plot_CE_urban_FDiv <-
  rbind(effect_urban_FDiv$FDiv,
        conditional_urban_FDiv) |>
  group_by(intervention, total_effect) |>
  transmute(mu = mean(est),
            li = quantile(est, 0.025),
            ls = quantile(est, 0.975)) |>
```

```

unique() |>
ggplot() +
geom_errorbar(aes(intervention, ymin = li, ymax = ls,
                  color = total_effect), width = 0,
              position = position_dodge(width = 0.3)) +
geom_point(aes(intervention, mu, color = total_effect),
           position = position_dodge(width = 0.3)) +
scale_color_manual(values = c('tan1', 'lightblue')) +
scale_fill_manual(values = c('tan1', 'lightblue')) +
theme_classic() +
labs(x = 'Intervention of\n infrastructure cover',
     y = 'FDiv') +
lims(y = c(-0.7, 2)) +
geom_hline(yintercept = 0, linetype = 3) +
theme(legend.position = 'none',
      legend.title = element_blank(),
      panel.grid = element_blank(),
      axis.line = element_line(linewidth = 0.25))

# figure urban FDiv

plot_urban_FDiv <-
  plot_grid(plot_cond_urban_S_FDiv,
            plot_cond_urban_FDiv,
            plot_CE_urban_FDiv, ncol = 3,
            labels = c('(i)', '(ii)', '(iii)'),
            label_fontface = 'plain',
            label_size = 10,
            label_x = 0.175)

```

S6.5.2.1 Summary causal effect urbanization

```

cont_urban_FDiv <- na.omit(effect_urban_FDiv$FDiv)

conditional_urban_FDiv <- na.omit(conditional_urban_FDiv)

diff_urban_FDiv <- cont_urban_FDiv$est - conditional_urban_FDiv$est

knitr::kable(
  tribble(~ value, ~estimation,
          'P(total effect < 0)', mean(cont_urban_FDiv$est < 0),

```

```

'mu total effect', mean(cont_urban_FDiv$est),
'sd total effect', sd(cont_urban_FDiv$est),
'AVG change relative to maximum (total) (%)',
mean(cont_urban_FDiv$porcentaje),
'SD change relative to maximum (total) (%)',
sd(cont_urban_FDiv$porcentaje),
'P(conditional effect < 0)', mean(conditional_urban_FDiv$est < 0),
'mu conditional effect', mean(conditional_urban_FDiv$est),
'sd conditional effect', sd(conditional_urban_FDiv$est),
'AVG change relative to maximum (conditional) (%)',
mean(conditional_urban_FDiv$porcentaje),
'SD change relative to maximum (conditional) (%)',
sd(conditional_urban_FDiv$porcentaje),
'P(total < conditional)',
mean(cont_urban_FDiv$est < conditional_urban_FDiv$est),
'AVG diff total-conditional (%)',
mean(diff_urban_FDiv)*100 / mean(cont_urban_FDiv$est)), digits = 2,
caption = 'Summary of causal effect'
)

```

Table S7: Summary of causal effect

value	estimation
P(total effect < 0)	0.98
mu total effect	-0.27
sd total effect	0.12
AVG change relative to maximum (total) (%)	-22.28
SD change relative to maximum (total) (%)	11.54
P(conditional effect < 0)	0.96
mu conditional effect	-0.22
sd conditional effect	0.13
AVG change relative to maximum (conditional) (%)	-18.45
SD change relative to maximum (conditional) (%)	11.50
P(total < conditional)	0.87
AVG diff total-conditional (%)	18.92

S6.5.3 Crop size

```
effect_crop_FDiv <- causal_effect_FDiv('beta_crop_S',
                                       'beta_crop_FDiv',
                                       dat2$crop, 'crop', T, negative = F)
```

Calculating total effect

Calculating total effect

```
effect_crop_FDiv$FDiv$total_effect <- 'Total effect'
```

```
conditional_crop_FDiv <- causal_effect_FDiv('beta_crop_S',
                                             'beta_crop_FDiv',
                                             dat2$crop, 'crop', F,
                                             negative = F)[[1]]
```

Calculating conditional effect

Calculating conditional effect

```
conditional_crop_FDiv$total_effect <- 'Conditional effect'
```

```
plot_CE_crop_FDiv <-
  rbind(effect_crop_FDiv$FDiv,
        conditional_crop_FDiv) |>
  group_by(intervention, total_effect) |>
  transmute(mu = mean(est),
            li = quantile(est, 0.025),
            ls = quantile(est, 0.975)) |>
  unique() |>
  ggplot() +
  geom_errorbar(aes(intervention, ymin = li, ymax = ls,
                   color = total_effect), width = 0,
               position = position_dodge(width = 0.3)) +
  geom_point(aes(intervention, mu, color = total_effect),
            position = position_dodge(width = 0.3)) +
  scale_color_manual(values = c('tan1', 'lightblue')) +
  scale_fill_manual(values = c('tan1', 'lightblue')) +
  lims(y = c(-0.7, 2.5)) +
  theme_classic() +
  labs(x = 'Intervention of\n crop size',
```

```

    y = 'FDiv') +
  geom_hline(yintercept = 0, linetype = 3) +
  theme(legend.position = 'none',
        legend.title = element_blank(),
        panel.grid = element_blank(),
        axis.line = element_line(linewidth = 0.25))

# figure crop FDiv

plot_crop_FDiv <-
  plot_grid(plot_cond_crop_S_FDiv,
            plot_cond_crop_FDiv,
            plot_CE_crop_FDiv, ncol = 3,
            labels = c('(i)', '(ii)', '(iii)'),
            label_fontface = 'plain',
            label_size = 10,
            label_x = 0.175)

```

S6.5.3.1 Summary causal effect tree cover

```

cont_crop_FDiv <- na.omit(effect_crop_FDiv$FDiv)

conditional_crop_FDiv <- na.omit(conditional_crop_FDiv)

diff_crop_FDiv <- cont_crop_FDiv$est - conditional_crop_FDiv$est

knitr::kable(
  tribble(~ value, ~estimation,
          'P(total effect > 0)', mean(cont_crop_FDiv$est > 0),
          'mu total effect', mean(cont_crop_FDiv$est),
          'sd total effect', sd(cont_crop_FDiv$est),
          'AVG change relative to maximum (total) (%)',
          mean(cont_crop_FDiv$porcentaje),
          'SD change relative to maximum (total) (%)',
          sd(cont_crop_FDiv$porcentaje),
          'P(conditional effect > 0)', mean(conditional_crop_FDiv$est > 0),
          'mu conditional effect', mean(conditional_crop_FDiv$est),
          'sd conditional effect', sd(conditional_crop_FDiv$est),
          'AVG change relative to maximum (conditional) (%)',
          mean(conditional_crop_FDiv$porcentaje),

```

```

'SD change relative to maximum (conditional) (%)',
sd(conditional_crop_FDiv$porcentaje),
'P(total > conditional)',
mean(cont_crop_FDiv$est > conditional_crop_FDiv$est),
'AVG diff total-conditional (%)',
mean(diff_crop_FDiv)*100 / mean(cont_crop_FDiv$est)), digits = 2,
caption = 'Summary of causal effect'
)

```

Table S8: Summary of causal effect

value	estimation
P(total effect > 0)	0.92
mu total effect	0.29
sd total effect	0.20
AVG change relative to maximum (total) (%)	15.84
SD change relative to maximum (total) (%)	10.95
P(conditional effect > 0)	0.88
mu conditional effect	0.25
sd conditional effect	0.20
AVG change relative to maximum (conditional) (%)	14.19
SD change relative to maximum (conditional) (%)	12.04
P(total > conditional)	0.76
AVG diff total-conditional (%)	12.84

7 Section 7: Figure 3

Code reproducing the figure in the main document.

```

plot_grid(plot_heigh_FDiv,
plot_urban_FDiv,
plot_crop_FDiv,
ncol = 1,
labels = c('(a)', '(b)', '(c)'),
label_size = 12,
label_fontface = 'plain',
label_x = -0.007)

```


Figure S10: Intrinsic (a) and extrinsic (b, c) drivers influencing the functional divergence (FDiv) and species richness (S) of birds foraging on an *S. terebinthifolia* population. Effects on S (a-i to c-i iii) imply indirect effects (i.e., $X \rightarrow S \rightarrow \text{FDiv}$) on FDiv, whereas effects on FDiv (a-ii to c-ii) denote direct effects (a i-ii, b i-ii and c i-ii). The dots indicate observed values, the solid line is the average estimation, the inner bands include 95% CI of the estimation, and the outer bands show 95% CI of the prediction. Error bars and dots in a-iii, b-iii, and c-iii show 95% credibility intervals and average values of the causal effect of intervening factors to minimum and maximum values; the contrast shows the difference between such interventions. The total effect implies both direct and indirect effects of factor i on FDiv. In contrast, the conditional effect denotes the direct effect of factor i on FDiv while holding S on the minimum value.

8 Section 8: Model FReg

Formatting the data frame in a list object.

```
dat3 <- dat_1

indx_na_FReg <- dat3$ind_id[which(is.na(dat3$freg_obs_22))]

dist_inds_FReg <- dist_inds[-indx_na_FReg, -indx_na_FReg]

dat3 <- dat3[-indx_na_FReg ,]

dat3$ind_id <- 1:nrow(dat3)

colnames(dist_inds_FReg) <- paste0('Ind', dat3$ind_id)
rownames(dist_inds_FReg) <- paste0('Ind', dat3$ind_id)

dat3 <- lapply(dat3, function(x) x)

dat3$N <- length(dat3$ind_id)
dat3$N_ind <- max(dat3$ind_id)
dat3$dist_mat <- dist_inds_FReg
names(dat3)[2:4] <- c('fric', 'fdiv', 'freg')
dat3$freg <- as.vector(scale(dat3$freg))

dat2$N <- length(dat2$ind_id)
dat2$N_ind <- max(dat2$ind_id)
dat2$dist_mat <- dist_inds_FDiv
names(dat2)[2:4] <- c('fric', 'fdiv', 'freg')
dat2$fdiv <- as.vector(scale(log(dat2$fdiv)))
```

Warning in log(dat2\$fdiv): NaNs produced

S8.1 Stan code

```
cat(file = 'model_FReg.stan',
    '\n\n',
    'functions {\n',
    '  matrix cov_GPL2(matrix x,\n',
    '                  real eta,
```

```

    real rho,
    real delta) {

    int N = dims(x)[1];
    matrix[N, N] K;
    matrix[N, N] L_K;

    for (i in 1:(N-1)) {
        K[i, i] = eta + delta;
        for (j in (i+1):N) {
            K[i, j] = eta * exp(-rho * square(x[i, j]));
            K[j, i] = K[i, j];
        }
    }

    K[N, N] = eta + delta;
    L_K = cholesky_decompose(K);
    return L_K;
}

data {
    int N;
    int N_ind;
    matrix[N_ind, N_ind] dist_mat;
    array[N] int ind_id;
    vector[N] freg;
    vector[N] s_std;
    vector[N] height;
    vector[N] crop;
    vector[N] duration;
    vector[N] fruit;
    vector[N] tree;
    vector[N] infrastructure;
}

parameters {
    // model S
    real alpha_S;
    real<lower = 0> sigma_S;
    real beta_forest_S;

```

```

real beta_height_S;
real beta_crop_S;
real beta_duration_S;
real beta_fruit_S;
real beta_urban_S;
vector[N_ind] z_ind_S;
real<lower = 0> eta_S;
real<lower = 0> rho_S;

// model FReg
real alpha_FReg;
real<lower = 0> sigma_FReg;
real beta_S;
real beta_forest_FReg;
real beta_height_FReg;
real beta_crop_FReg;
real beta_duration_FReg;
real beta_fruit_FReg;
real beta_urban_FReg;
vector[N_ind] z_ind_FReg;
real<lower = 0> eta_FReg;
real<lower = 0> rho_FReg;
}

transformed parameters {
  // pars S
  vector[N_ind] ind_S;
  matrix[N_ind, N_ind] L_K_S;
  L_K_S = cov_GPL2(dist_mat, eta_S, rho_S, 0.001);
  ind_S = L_K_S * z_ind_S;

  // pars FReg
  vector[N_ind] ind_FReg;
  matrix[N_ind, N_ind] L_K_FReg;
  L_K_FReg = cov_GPL2(dist_mat, eta_FReg, rho_FReg, 0.001);
  ind_FReg = L_K_FReg * z_ind_FReg;
}

model {

  // prior S
  alpha_S ~ normal(0, 1);

```

```

sigma_S ~ exponential(1);
z_ind_S ~ normal(0, 0.25);
eta_S ~ exponential(4);
rho_S ~ exponential(1);
beta_forest_S ~ normal(0, 0.25);
beta_height_S ~ normal(0, 0.25);
beta_crop_S ~ normal(0, 0.25);
beta_duration_S ~ normal(0, 0.25);
beta_fruit_S ~ normal(0, 0.25);
beta_urban_S ~ normal(0, 0.25);

// prior FReg
alpha_FReg ~ normal(0, 1);
sigma_FReg ~ exponential(1);
z_ind_FReg ~ normal(0, 0.25);
eta_FReg ~ exponential(4);
rho_FReg ~ exponential(1);
beta_forest_FReg ~ normal(0, 0.25);
beta_height_FReg ~ normal(0, 0.25);
beta_crop_FReg ~ normal(0, 0.25);
beta_duration_FReg ~ normal(0, 0.25);
beta_fruit_FReg ~ normal(0, 0.25);
beta_urban_FReg ~ normal(0, 0.25);
beta_S ~ normal(0, 1);

// model S
s_std ~ student_t(7,
                  alpha_S +
                  beta_forest_S * tree +
                  beta_height_S * height +
                  beta_crop_S * crop +
                  beta_duration_S * duration +
                  beta_fruit_S * fruit +
                  beta_urban_S * infrastructure +
                  ind_S[ind_id], sigma_S);

// model FReg
freg ~ student_t(7,
                 alpha_FReg +
                 beta_S * s_std +
                 beta_forest_FReg * tree +
                 beta_height_FReg * height +

```

```

        beta_crop_FReg * crop +
        beta_duration_FReg * duration +
        beta_fruit_FReg * fruit +
        beta_urban_FReg * infrastructure +
        ind_FReg[ind_id], sigma_FReg);
}

generated quantities {
  array[N] real ppcheck_S;
  array[N] real ppcheck_FReg;
  vector[N] mu_S;
  vector[N] mu_FReg;

  mu_S = alpha_S +
        beta_forest_S * tree +
        beta_height_S * height +
        beta_crop_S * crop +
        beta_duration_S * duration +
        beta_fruit_S * fruit +
        beta_urban_S * infrastructure +
        ind_S[ind_id];

  ppcheck_S = student_t_rng(7, mu_S, sigma_S);

  mu_FReg = alpha_FReg +
           beta_S * s_std +
           beta_forest_FReg * tree +
           beta_height_FReg * height +
           beta_crop_FReg * crop +
           beta_duration_FReg * duration +
           beta_fruit_FReg * fruit +
           beta_urban_FReg * infrastructure +
           ind_FReg[ind_id];

  ppcheck_FReg = student_t_rng(7, mu_FReg, sigma_FReg);
}
')
```

S8.2 Fitting the model

```
file <- paste0(getwd(), '/model_FReg.stan')
fit_FReg <- cmdstan_model(file, compile = T)

indx_na_vars <-
  unlist(lapply(dat3, function(x) sum(is.na(x)) == 0),
         use.names = F)

mod_FReg <-
  fit_FReg$sample(
    data = dat3[indx_na_vars],
    iter_warmup = 500,
    iter_sampling = 4e3,
    chains = 3,
    parallel_chains = 3,
    thin = 3,
    seed = 5
  )
```

S8.3 Model diagnostics

```
sum_FReg <- mod_FReg$summary()
```

```
Warning: The ESS has been capped to avoid unstable estimates.
Warning: The ESS has been capped to avoid unstable estimates.
Warning: The ESS has been capped to avoid unstable estimates.
```

```
mod_diagnostics(mod_FReg, sum_FReg)
```


Figure S11: Rhat values vs effective sampling size (ess). Rhat < 1.05 indicates that the Markov Chains converged to the same stationary distribution. ess must be at least 100 in order to be reliable

```

indx_pars <-
  c(grep('^beta', sum_FReg$variable),
    grep('^sigma', sum_FReg$variable),
    grep('^alpha', sum_FReg$variable),
    grep('^ind', sum_FReg$variable))

par(mfrow = c(4, 5), mar = c(4, 4, 1, 1))
for (i in 1:17) {
  trace_plot(mod_FReg, sum_FReg$variable[indx_pars[i]], 3)
}
par(mfrow = c(1, 1))

```


Figure S12: Trace plots showing chain convergence per parameter

```

ppcheck_S <- mod_FReg$draws('ppcheck_S', format = 'matrix')
ppcheck_FReg <- mod_FReg$draws('ppcheck_FReg', format = 'matrix')

par(mfrow = c(1, 2), mar = c(4, 4, 1, 1))
plot(density(dat3$s_std), xlim = c(-4, 5),
     ylim = c(0, 0.7), main = '', xlab = 'N species (z-scores)')
for (i in 1:500) lines(density(ppcheck_S[i, ]), lwd = 0.1)
lines(density(dat3$s_std), col = 'red', lwd = 1.5)

plot(density(dat3$freg), xlim = c(-5, 5),
     ylim = c(0, 0.7), main = '', xlab = 'FReg (z-scores)')
for (i in 1:500) lines(density(ppcheck_FReg[i, ]), lwd = 0.1)
lines(density(dat3$freg), col = 'red', lwd = 1.5)

```


Figure S13: Posterior predictive checks of the model describing species richness and FReg of the birds assemblage

```
par(mfrow = c(1, 1))
```

```
par(mfrow = c(2, 2))
plot(density(apply(ppcheck_S, 1, mean)), xlab = 'AVG. S (estimated)',
     main = '')
abline(v = mean(dat3$s_std), col = 'red')
plot(density(apply(ppcheck_S, 1, sd)), xlab = 'SD. S (estimated)',
     main = '')
abline(v = sd(dat3$s_std), col = 'red')

plot(density(apply(ppcheck_FReg, 1, mean)), xlab = 'AVG. FReg (estimated)',
     main = '')
abline(v = mean(dat3$freg), col = 'red')
plot(density(apply(ppcheck_FReg, 1, sd)), xlab = 'SD. FReg (estimated)',
     main = '')
abline(v = sd(dat3$freg), col = 'red')
```


Figure S14: Observed average and SD from species richness and FReg against the estimated by the model

```
par(mfrow = c(1, 1))
```

```
text <- 'Average, SD, confidence intervals and metrics
of sampling diagnostics for the parameters estimating
species richness and FReg of the birds assemblage'
```

```
knitr::kable(
  sum_FReg[indx_pars, ],
  digits = 2,
  caption = text
)
```

Table S9: Average, SD, confidence intervals and metrics of sampling diagnostics for the parameters estimating species richness and FReg of the birds assemblage

variable	mean	median	sd	mad	q5	q95	rhat	ess_bulk	ess_tail
beta_forest_S	0.03	0.03	0.16	0.15	-0.22	0.29	1	4154.65	3777.03
beta_height_S	0.07	0.07	0.17	0.17	-0.21	0.35	1	4158.13	3735.94

variable	mean	median	sd	mad	q5	q95	rhat	ess_bulk	ess_tail
beta_crop_S	0.08	0.08	0.16	0.16	-0.17	0.36	1	4146.63	3879.96
beta_duration_S	0.17	0.17	0.18	0.18	-0.14	0.45	1	4114.35	3870.70
beta_fruit_S	0.08	0.07	0.17	0.17	-0.20	0.37	1	4151.49	3597.79
beta_urban_S	-0.13	-0.13	0.17	0.18	-0.41	0.16	1	4159.25	3839.53
beta_S	-0.81	-0.81	0.25	0.24	-1.23	-0.41	1	3366.99	3201.62
beta_forest_FReg	0.07	0.08	0.17	0.17	-0.21	0.35	1	4101.82	4149.77
beta_height_FReg	-0.10	-0.11	0.18	0.18	-0.39	0.20	1	4477.12	3932.54
beta_crop_FReg	0.13	0.12	0.15	0.15	-0.12	0.38	1	3909.62	3448.83
beta_duration_FReg	0.05	0.06	0.17	0.17	-0.24	0.33	1	4191.55	3757.08
beta_fruit_FReg	0.05	0.05	0.16	0.16	-0.21	0.32	1	4116.38	3705.83
beta_urban_FReg	-0.08	-0.08	0.18	0.17	-0.38	0.22	1	4389.93	3765.09
sigma_S	0.72	0.70	0.15	0.14	0.50	0.99	1	4043.82	3918.04
sigma_FReg	0.75	0.73	0.15	0.14	0.54	1.02	1	4309.80	3815.41
alpha_S	0.23	0.22	0.18	0.17	-0.05	0.52	1	4319.65	3923.12
alpha_FReg	0.27	0.28	0.19	0.19	-0.05	0.58	1	4254.36	3934.80
ind_S[1]	-0.02	-0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.23	0.16	1	4215.05	3408.03
ind_S[2]	-0.02	-0.01	0.13	0.09	-0.24	0.16	1	4615.08	3825.30
ind_S[3]	0.01	0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.19	0.22	1	3875.68	4058.29
ind_S[4]	-0.01	0.00	0.12	0.09	-0.20	0.19	1	4746.03	3757.91
ind_S[5]	0.02	0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.16	0.24	1	4365.00	3902.23
ind_S[6]	-0.01	-0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.20	0.18	1	4469.39	3646.98
ind_S[7]	0.01	0.00	0.12	0.09	-0.19	0.21	1	4550.52	3814.56
ind_S[8]	0.01	0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.19	0.22	1	4895.95	4174.03
ind_S[9]	0.03	0.02	0.13	0.09	-0.16	0.27	1	4292.25	3617.26
ind_S[10]	0.01	0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.18	0.21	1	4589.56	3855.50
ind_S[11]	-0.01	-0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.22	0.17	1	4521.99	3460.63
ind_S[12]	0.03	0.02	0.13	0.09	-0.16	0.25	1	4416.11	3935.04
ind_S[13]	-0.01	-0.01	0.13	0.09	-0.23	0.18	1	4564.91	3952.48
ind_S[14]	-0.02	-0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.23	0.17	1	4200.58	3817.09
ind_S[15]	0.03	0.02	0.13	0.09	-0.15	0.26	1	4180.09	3248.32
ind_S[16]	-0.03	-0.01	0.13	0.09	-0.25	0.16	1	4444.33	3891.76
ind_S[17]	0.01	0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.18	0.22	1	4379.01	3895.13
ind_S[18]	-0.01	-0.01	0.12	0.08	-0.22	0.18	1	4447.27	3789.17
ind_S[19]	-0.01	-0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.22	0.18	1	4254.09	4056.14
ind_S[20]	-0.01	-0.01	0.13	0.09	-0.23	0.18	1	4142.55	3503.56
ind_S[21]	0.00	0.00	0.12	0.09	-0.20	0.20	1	4141.09	3791.32
ind_S[22]	0.02	0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.17	0.23	1	4216.98	3759.70
ind_FReg[1]	-0.02	-0.01	0.13	0.10	-0.24	0.18	1	4007.77	3683.40
ind_FReg[2]	0.02	0.01	0.13	0.09	-0.17	0.24	1	4280.00	3376.44
ind_FReg[3]	-0.02	-0.01	0.13	0.09	-0.24	0.17	1	4615.92	3853.09
ind_FReg[4]	0.02	0.01	0.13	0.09	-0.17	0.25	1	4477.49	3792.06

variable	mean	median	sd	mad	q5	q95	rhat	ess_bulk	ess_tail
ind_FReg[5]	0.01	0.01	0.13	0.09	-0.19	0.23	1	4610.18	3878.61
ind_FReg[6]	-0.02	-0.01	0.13	0.09	-0.23	0.17	1	4703.77	3879.81
ind_FReg[7]	0.03	0.02	0.13	0.10	-0.17	0.25	1	4400.40	3439.67
ind_FReg[8]	0.02	0.01	0.13	0.09	-0.17	0.25	1	4809.20	3687.49
ind_FReg[9]	0.02	0.01	0.13	0.10	-0.18	0.25	1	4235.55	3812.31
ind_FReg[10]	-0.02	-0.01	0.13	0.09	-0.24	0.17	1	4517.97	3840.97
ind_FReg[11]	0.02	0.01	0.13	0.09	-0.17	0.24	1	3937.18	3764.08
ind_FReg[12]	0.00	0.00	0.13	0.09	-0.20	0.22	1	4269.78	3961.23
ind_FReg[13]	-0.02	-0.01	0.12	0.09	-0.23	0.18	1	4216.37	3822.80
ind_FReg[14]	0.02	0.01	0.13	0.09	-0.17	0.25	1	4591.50	3680.57
ind_FReg[15]	-0.03	-0.02	0.13	0.09	-0.26	0.17	1	4157.91	3483.16
ind_FReg[16]	0.02	0.01	0.13	0.09	-0.17	0.24	1	4044.44	3587.78
ind_FReg[17]	-0.02	-0.01	0.13	0.09	-0.24	0.17	1	4092.36	3657.79
ind_FReg[18]	-0.01	-0.01	0.13	0.09	-0.22	0.19	1	4458.07	3784.04
ind_FReg[19]	-0.01	-0.01	0.13	0.09	-0.23	0.19	1	4251.44	3748.40
ind_FReg[20]	0.01	0.00	0.12	0.09	-0.19	0.21	1	4640.73	3779.33
ind_FReg[21]	-0.02	-0.01	0.13	0.09	-0.23	0.19	1	3911.88	3932.97
ind_FReg[22]	-0.03	-0.02	0.13	0.09	-0.25	0.17	1	4103.98	3736.90

S8.4 Conditional effects

S8.4.1 Crop size

```

post_FReg <- mod_FReg$draws(sum_FReg[indx_pars, ]$variable, format = 'df')

post_FReg <- post_FReg[, sum_FReg[indx_pars, ]$variable]

conditional_effect_FReg <-
  function(par, x_var, N = 500, FReg = T) {

    x <- seq(min(x_var), max(x_var), length.out = N)

    ind_FReg <- grep('^ind_FReg', colnames(post_FReg))
    ind_S <- grep('^ind_S', colnames(post_FReg))

    est <-
      lapply(x, FUN =
        function(i) {
          if (FReg) {

```

```

    mu_ <-
      post_FReg$alpha_FReg +
      post_FReg[[par]] * i +
      apply(post_FReg[, ind_FReg], 1, mean)

    mu_pred <-
      rstudent(N, 7, mu_, post_FReg$sigma_FReg)
  } else {
    mu_ <-
      post_FReg$alpha_S +
      post_FReg[[par]] * i +
      apply(post_FReg[, ind_S], 1, mean)

    mu_pred <-
      rstudent(N, 7, mu_, post_FReg$sigma_S)
  }

  tibble(mu = mean(mu_),
         li = quantile(mu_, 0.025),
         ls = quantile(mu_, 0.975),
         li_pred = quantile(mu_pred, 0.025),
         ls_pred = quantile(mu_pred, 0.975))
})
est <- do.call('rbind', est)
est$x <- x
est
}

est_height_FDiv <- conditional_effect_FDiv('beta_height_FDiv',
                                          dat2$height, FDiv = T)
est_height_S_FDiv <- conditional_effect_FDiv('beta_height_S',
                                             dat2$height, FDiv = F)

plot_cond_height_FDiv <-
  ggplot() +
  geom_ribbon(data = est_height_FDiv,
            aes(x, mu, ymin = li_pred, ymax = ls_pred),
            alpha = 0.5, fill = 'lightblue2') +
  geom_ribbon(data = est_height_S_FDiv,
            aes(x, mu, ymin = li, ymax = ls),

```

```

      alpha = 0.7, fill = 'lightblue') +
geom_line(data = est_height_FDiv,
          aes(x, mu), color = 'tan1', linewidth = 1, alpha = 0.7) +
geom_point(data = tibble(x = dat2$height,
                        y = dat2$fdiv),
           aes(x, y), color = 'tan1', alpha = 0.5) +
theme_classic() +
labs(x = 'Tree height (z-scores)',
     y = 'FDiv (z-scores)') +
theme(legend.position = c(0.2, 0.9),
      legend.title = element_blank(),
      panel.grid = element_blank(),
      axis.line = element_line(linewidth = 0.25))

plot_cond_heighth_S_FDiv <-
  ggplot() +
  geom_ribbon(data = est_height_S_FDiv,
            aes(x, mu, ymin = li_pred, ymax = ls_pred),
            alpha = 0.5, fill = 'lightblue2') +
  geom_ribbon(data = est_height_S_FDiv,
            aes(x, mu, ymin = li, ymax = ls),
            alpha = 0.7, fill = 'lightblue') +
  geom_line(data = est_height_S_FDiv,
           aes(x, mu), color = 'tan1', linewidth = 1, alpha = 0.7) +
  geom_point(data = tibble(x = dat2$height,
                          y = dat2$s_std),
            aes(x, y), color = 'tan1', alpha = 0.5) +
  theme_classic() +
  labs(x = 'Tree height (z-scores)',
       y = 'S (z-scores)') +
  theme(legend.position = c(0.2, 0.9),
        legend.title = element_blank(),
        panel.grid = element_blank(),
        axis.line = element_line(linewidth = 0.25))

est_crop_FReg <- conditional_effect_FReg('beta_crop_FReg',
                                       dat3$crop, FReg = T)
est_crop_S_FReg <- conditional_effect_FReg('beta_crop_S',
                                       dat3$crop, FReg = F)

plot_cond_crop_FReg <-
  ggplot() +

```

```

geom_ribbon(data = est_crop_FReg,
           aes(x, mu, ymin = li_pred, ymax = ls_pred),
           alpha = 0.5, fill = 'lightblue2') +
geom_ribbon(data = est_crop_FReg,
           aes(x, mu, ymin = li, ymax = ls),
           alpha = 0.7, fill = 'lightblue') +
geom_line(data = est_crop_FReg,
          aes(x, mu), color = 'tan1', linewidth = 1, alpha = 0.7) +
geom_point(data = tibble(x = dat3$crop,
                        y = dat3$freg),
           aes(x, y), color = 'tan1', alpha = 0.5) +
theme_classic() +
labs(x = 'Crop size (z-scores)',
     y = 'FReg (z-scores)') +
theme(legend.position = c(0.2, 0.9),
      legend.title = element_blank(),
      panel.grid = element_blank(),
      axis.line = element_line(linewidth = 0.25))

plot_cond_crop_S_FReg <-
  ggplot() +
  geom_ribbon(data = est_crop_S_FReg,
            aes(x, mu, ymin = li_pred, ymax = ls_pred),
            alpha = 0.5, fill = 'lightblue2') +
  geom_ribbon(data = est_crop_S_FReg,
            aes(x, mu, ymin = li, ymax = ls),
            alpha = 0.7, fill = 'lightblue') +
  geom_line(data = est_crop_S_FReg,
           aes(x, mu), color = 'tan1', linewidth = 1, alpha = 0.7) +
  geom_point(data = tibble(x = dat3$crop,
                          y = dat3$s_std),
            aes(x, y), color = 'tan1', alpha = 0.5) +
  theme_classic() +
  labs(x = 'Crop size (z-scores)',
       y = 'S (z-scores)') +
  theme(legend.position = c(0.2, 0.9),
        legend.title = element_blank(),
        panel.grid = element_blank(),
        axis.line = element_line(linewidth = 0.25))

```

S8.5 Causal effect

S8.5.1 Crop size

```
causal_effect_FReg <-  
  function(par_EQ1, par_EQ2, x_var, x_label, total_effect = T) {  
    ind_s <- grep('^ind_S', colnames(post_FReg))  
    ind_FReg <- grep('^ind_FReg', colnames(post_FReg))  
    mu_S <- mean(d$S)  
    SD_S <- sd(d$S)  
  
    FReg <- dat_1$freg_obs_22[-which(is.na(dat_1$freg_obs_22))]  
  
    mu_FReg <- mean(FReg)  
    SD_FReg <- sd(FReg)  
  
    estimated <-  
      lapply(c(min, max), FUN =  
            function(.fun) {  
  
                est_S <-  
                  post_FReg$alpha_S +  
                  post_FReg[[par_EQ1]] * .fun(x_var) +  
                  apply(post_FReg[, ind_s], 1, mean)  
  
                if (total_effect) {  
                  message('Calculating total effect')  
                } else {  
                  message('Calculating conditional effect')  
                  est_S <- min(dat3$s_std)  
                }  
  
                est_FReg <-  
                  post_FReg$alpha_FReg +  
                  post_FReg$beta_S * est_S +  
                  post_FReg[[par_EQ2]] * .fun(x_var) +  
                  apply(post_FReg[, ind_FReg], 1, mean)  
  
                est_FReg <- mu_FReg + est_FReg * SD_FReg  
                est_S <- mu_S + est_S * SD_S  
            })  
  }
```

```

        list(S = tibble(est = est_S,
                        Y = 'S',
                        X = x_label),
             FReg = tibble(est = est_FReg,
                           Y = 'FReg',
                           X = x_label))

    })

names(estimated) <- c('Min', 'Max')

estimated <-
  lapply(names(estimated), FUN =
    function(x) {
      d <- estimated[[x]]
      d$$intervention <- x
      d$FReg$intervention <- x
      d
    })
names(estimated) <- c('Min', 'Max')

estimated <-
  lapply(estimated, FUN =
    function(x) {
      do.call('rbind', x)
    })
estimated <- do.call('rbind', estimated)
estimated <- split(estimated, estimated$Y)
lapply(estimated, FUN =
  function(x) {
    x2 <- x[x$intervention == 'Max', ]
    x2$est <-
      x[x$intervention == 'Max', ]$est -
      x[x$intervention == 'Min', ]$est

    x2$intervention <- 'Contrast'
    z <- (x2$est * 100)/x[x$intervention == 'Max', ]$est
    x$porcentaje <- NA
    x2$porcentaje <- z
    x2 <- rbind(x, x2)
    x2$intervention <- as.factor(x2$intervention)
    x2$intervention <- factor(x2$intervention,

```

```

                                levels = c('Min', 'Max',
                                             'Contrast'))
                                x2
                                })
}

effect_crop_FReg <- causal_effect_FReg('beta_crop_S',
                                       'beta_crop_FReg',
                                       dat3$crop, 'crop', T)

```

Calculating total effect
Calculating total effect

```

effect_crop_FReg$FReg$total_effect <- 'Total effect'

conditional_crop_FReg <- causal_effect_FReg('beta_crop_S',
                                           'beta_crop_FReg',
                                           dat3$crop, 'crop', F)[[1]]

```

Calculating conditional effect

Calculating conditional effect

```

conditional_crop_FReg$total_effect <- 'Conditional effect'

plot_CE_crop_FReg <-
  rbind(effect_crop_FReg$FReg,
        conditional_crop_FReg) |>
  group_by(intervention, total_effect) |>
  transmute(mu = mean(est),
            li = quantile(est, 0.025),
            ls = quantile(est, 0.975)) |>
  unique() |>
  ggplot() +
  geom_errorbar(aes(intervention, ymin = li, ymax = ls,
                   color = total_effect), width = 0,
               position = position_dodge(width = 0.3)) +
  geom_point(aes(intervention, mu, color = total_effect),
            position = position_dodge(width = 0.3)) +
  scale_color_manual(values = c('tan1', 'lightblue')) +

```

```

scale_fill_manual(values = c('tan1', 'lightblue')) +
lims(y = c(-0.5, 1.5)) +
theme_classic() +
labs(x = 'Intervention of crop size',
     y = 'FReg') +
geom_hline(yintercept = 0, linetype = 3) +
theme(legend.position = c(0.37, 0.875),
     legend.background = element_blank(),
     legend.title = element_blank(),
     panel.grid = element_blank(),
     axis.line = element_line(linewidth = 0.25))

```

S8.5.1.1 Summary causal crop size

```

cont_crop_FReg <- na.omit(effect_crop_FReg$FReg)

conditional_crop_FReg <- na.omit(conditional_crop_FReg)

diff_crop_FReg <- conditional_crop_FReg$est - cont_crop_FReg$est

knitr::kable(
  tribble(~ value,           ~estimation,
    'P(total effect > 0)', mean(cont_crop_FReg$est > 0),
    'mu total effect', mean(cont_crop_FReg$est),
    'sd total effect', sd(cont_crop_FReg$est),
    'AVG change relative to maximum (total) (%)',
    mean(cont_crop_FReg$porcentaje),
    'SD change relative to maximum (total) (%)',
    sd(cont_crop_FReg$porcentaje),
    'P(conditional effect > 0)', mean(conditional_crop_FReg$est > 0),
    'mu conditional effect', mean(conditional_crop_FReg$est),
    'sd conditional effect', sd(conditional_crop_FReg$est),
    'AVG change relative to maximum (conditional) (%)',
    mean(conditional_crop_FReg$porcentaje),
    'SD change relative to maximum (conditional) (%)',
    sd(conditional_crop_FReg$porcentaje),
    'P(total > conditional)',
    mean(cont_crop_FReg$est < conditional_crop_FReg$est),
    'AVG diff total-conditional (%)',
    100-(mean(diff_crop_FReg)*100 / mean(conditional_crop_FReg$est))),
  digits = 2, caption = 'Summary of causal effect'
)

```

)

Table S10: Summary of causal effect

value	estimation
P(total effect > 0)	0.61
mu total effect	0.04
sd total effect	0.14
AVG change relative to maximum (total) (%)	2.11
SD change relative to maximum (total) (%)	20.10
P(conditional effect > 0)	0.80
mu conditional effect	0.09
sd conditional effect	0.11
AVG change relative to maximum (conditional) (%)	8.52
SD change relative to maximum (conditional) (%)	11.18
P(total > conditional)	0.69
AVG diff total-conditional (%)	45.67

9 Section 9: Figure 4

```
plot_crop_FReg <-  
  plot_grid(plot_cond_crop_S_FReg,  
            plot_cond_crop_FReg,  
            plot_CE_crop_FReg, ncol = 3,  
            labels = c('(a)', '(b)', '(c)'),  
            label_fontface = 'plain',  
            label_size = 10,  
            label_x = 0.175)  
  
plot_crop_FReg
```


Figure S15: Indirect and direct effect of crop size on the functional regularity (FReg) and species richness (S) of birds foraging on an *S. terebinthifolia* population. The effect on S (a) and FReg (b) denote indirect (i.e., $X \rightarrow S \rightarrow FDiv$) and direct effects, respectively (a and b). The dots indicate observed values, the solid line is the average estimation, the inner bands include 95% CI of the estimation, and the outer bands show 95% CI of the prediction. (c) Error bars and dots show 95% credibility intervals and average values of the causal effect of intervening factors to minimum and maximum values; the contrast shows the difference between such interventions. The total effect implies both direct and indirect effects of crop size on FReg, whereas the conditional effect denotes the direct effect of crop size on FReg while holding S on the minimum value.

10 Section 10: Computational environment

```
sessionInfo()
```

```
R version 4.4.0 (2024-04-24 ucrt)
Platform: x86_64-w64-mingw32/x64
Running under: Windows 11 x64 (build 26100)
```

```
Matrix products: default
```

```
locale:
```

```
[1] LC_COLLATE=Spanish_Latin America.utf8
[2] LC_CTYPE=Spanish_Latin America.utf8
[3] LC_MONETARY=Spanish_Latin America.utf8
[4] LC_NUMERIC=C
[5] LC_TIME=Spanish_Latin America.utf8
```

```
time zone: America/Sao_Paulo
```

```
tzcode source: internal
```

```
attached base packages:
```

```
[1] parallel stats graphics grDevices utils datasets methods
[8] base
```

```
other attached packages:
```

```
[1] sf_1.0-16 readxl_1.4.3 cowplot_1.1.3 forcats_1.0.0
[5] magrittr_2.0.3 rethinking_2.40 posterior_1.6.0 cmdstanr_0.8.1
[9] patchwork_1.2.0 ggplot2_3.5.1 dplyr_1.1.4
```

```
loaded via a namespace (and not attached):
```

```
[1] tensorA_0.36.2.1 utf8_1.2.4 generics_0.1.3
[4] class_7.3-22 KernSmooth_2.23-22 shape_1.4.6.1
[7] lattice_0.22-6 digest_0.6.36 evaluate_1.0.3
[10] grid_4.4.0 mvtnorm_1.2-5 fastmap_1.2.0
[13] cellranger_1.1.0 jsonlite_1.8.8 processx_3.8.4
[16] e1071_1.7-14 backports_1.5.0 DBI_1.2.3
[19] ps_1.7.7 fansi_1.0.6 scales_1.3.0
[22] abind_1.4-5 cli_3.6.3 rlang_1.1.4
[25] units_0.8-5 munsell_0.5.1 withr_3.0.2
[28] yaml_2.3.9 tools_4.4.0 checkmate_2.3.1
```

[31]	<code>coda_0.19-4.1</code>	<code>colorspace_2.1-0</code>	<code>vctrs_0.6.5</code>
[34]	<code>R6_2.5.1</code>	<code>proxy_0.4-27</code>	<code>classInt_0.4-10</code>
[37]	<code>matrixStats_1.3.0</code>	<code>lifecycle_1.0.4</code>	<code>MASS_7.3-60.2</code>
[40]	<code>pkgconfig_2.0.3</code>	<code>pillar_1.9.0</code>	<code>gtable_0.3.5</code>
[43]	<code>data.table_1.15.4</code>	<code>Rcpp_1.0.12</code>	<code>loo_2.8.0</code>
[46]	<code>glue_1.7.0</code>	<code>xfun_0.45</code>	<code>tibble_3.2.1</code>
[49]	<code>tidyselect_1.2.1</code>	<code>rstudioapi_0.16.0</code>	<code>knitr_1.48</code>
[52]	<code>farver_2.1.2</code>	<code>htmltools_0.5.8.1</code>	<code>labeling_0.4.3</code>
[55]	<code>rmarkdown_2.27</code>	<code>compiler_4.4.0</code>	<code>distributional_0.4.0</code>